

VALKYRIES

D2.10 Harmonization and Standardization Reports M12

Reference Number: D2.10

Ed/Rev: A/1

Main Contributor: NOVOTEC

Other Contributors: SSSA, HESE, HRT, UMU, TASSICA, BDI

Date: 25/01/2023

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Ignacio Hernandez Palencia	ignacio.hernandez@novotec.es	NOVOTEC
Jose Cabezas Rodriguez	jose.cabezas@novotec.es	NOVOTEC
Angel Gimenez Celdran	angel.gimenez@novotec.es	NOVOTEC
Eugenio Herraiz Hervás	Eugenio.herraiz@novotec.es	NOVOTEC
Gustavo Amodeo Gonzalez	gustavo.amodeo@novotec.es	NOVOTEC

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Miguel Gaspar	HESE	Editing/Reviewing
Denise Amram	SSSA	Review
Iosif Vourvachis	HRT	Review
Dimitrios Iliadis	HRT	Review
UMU Team	UMU	WP4 inputs
Tassica Team	TAS	WP5 inputs
BDI Team	BDI	WP6 inputs
Manuel Ocaña Domínguez	INDRA	Quality review

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	20/09/2022	All	Original Document
A/1	25/01/2023	5.2 & 5.3	Comments from general project review consolidated report are addressed. New text and changes from previous version are highlighted in yellow for easy identification.

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, out comes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.10 *Harmonization and Standardization Reports M12* presents the status of the project in terms of standardisation and harmonisation.

The harmonization and standardization process are a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous competence/knowledge shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, specific procedures (and their differences between regions/countries), evaluation and information exchange.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Harmonization and Standardization Reports

Deliverable Id: D2.10

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D2.10

Name of lead participant: NOV

Name of Contributors: SSSA, HESE, HRT, UMU, TASSICA, BDI

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP2 Design Principles and Harmonization Tactics.

Linked project tasks: T2.5 Dynamic Harmonisation and Standardization

Action: Harmonisation

Status: Second Release (version A/1)

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document presents the status of the project in terms of standardisation and harmonisation in month 12.

3. Introduction

This deliverable is the **second** harmonisation and standardisation report. There will be a report every 6 months until the end of the project as it is defining in the programme.

The last report presented a first overview. Some aspects have changed since then. The tools that first seemed more useful have been replaced by others. The needs of the project have taken precedence over the methodology. So, the working methodology changes throughout the project in a process of continuous improvement to be as efficient and effective as possible.

One of the first deliverables on the harmonisation methodology D2.4, about the standardisation roadmap, provides an effective base for developing and controlling the harmonization process. It is necessary to keep it in mind for understanding the steps required on this and next deliverables.

The requirements and definition of the use cases have been agreed recently and the scope of the project has been defined in depth.

The technology work packages are very important as they provide the most progress in terms of harmonisation. The tasks of WP4, WP5 and WP6 are in the midterm of completion and the harmonisation report is substantial at the moment.

4. Objectives

The main objective of the deliverable is to report the progress of standardisation and harmonisation of Valkyries.

The secondary objectives of this report are:

- Collect the standardization actions that the partners are carrying out.
- Identify the lack of progress in some parts.
- Check that the project is in line with the roadmap.

5. Current status of the pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization.

The harmonisation and standardisation of the project is defined and in progress.

As a reminder of deliverable D2.4 about the standardisation roadmap. Novotec defined 3 phases for the harmonisation process. In this first harmonisation report we are understandably in the first harmonization phase.

The first phase of the harmonization, we are in the process of collecting information and mapping standards, is still working a providing more inputs to the second one.

The current state of standardisation and harmonisation is in the second phase: “Gaps and commonalties identification”. In this step the project produces gaps based on the analysed state of the art and the surveys made it to experts a final user.

In the following *Figure 1* we can see the harmonisation process of the project and we can identify the current phase of the project, as well as its future intended steps:

Figure 1 - Valkyries harmonisation process

The harmonisation processes of some areas are directly linked to one or more tasks. Almost all of these tasks fall under WP4, WP5 & WP6. As are in the midterm of the project.

The project is currently in the phase of identifying gaps and communities. A first approximation of gap-dependent opportunities has been made and in the next stages of the project will be developed.

To achieve this main objective, VALKYRIES is using the following tools and formats.

5.1. Legal standard identification

5.1.1. Formant description

This format collects information that affects the whole sector or the involved countries.

All the standards related to the project must be collected and all the standards that directly affects VALYRIES in the Use Cases (UC) must be collected too.

The information is sorted for every UCs and a common part with documents that are applicable for every UCs. This format could be filled out by all partners, although each partner will provide more information on their native country. Nevertheless, any partner could add the documents and information that may affect the project.

5.1.2. Current status M12

A large number of legal standards, procedures and laws have been collected in this first period. In total around 60 documents have been identified as relevant to the project.

The main part of the legal standards is already identified in M12. Although the document it is alive. More standards could be added if we find it.

These identified documents are very useful for define gaps because they provide a common point of discussion.

See Annex A: Legal standard Identification.

5.2. Pre-identification of gaps

5.2.1. Formant description

This format collected pre-identified gaps and commonalities detected by partners. Some data, like the aforementioned gaps and commonalities, can be detected before the meetings with the partners. This is because there is experience, literature and previous projects about these gaps and commonalities.

Smaller-scale drills could be organised in different countries to detect gaps before the use cases.

5.2.2. Current status M12

This format it is not active. This preliminary gap identification document has been transformed and has been the input for the gap identification. Differentiated within each WP and task.

This document it is not useful so that can't be find it in annex.

This information on the format "pre-identification of gaps" has been added for traceability between deliverable versions and for the harmonisation process.

5.3. Matrix tool

5.3.1. Formant description

This format is designed to make a comparison between the countries of the Use Cases in different areas will be made. Therefore, there will be a matrix tool for each Use Case (UC).

This collection of information was essential since it was the fundamental pillar of the analysis of the partners' methodology in both parts of the border.

This is a complex process due to the heterogeneity of the data. The first idea for this matrix is to make this comparison, the matrix tool will be used. For this reason, recorded and classified data will be compared. There are different types of matching depending on the type of data. The comparison will be different and the complexity of the data should be taken into account. It is not the same situation to compare. As in other formats, partners must provide the necessary information for the comparison. Nevertheless, each partner will bring more information from their native country.

5.3.2. Current status M12

This document doesn't have the expected progress due to its complexity and the heterogeneity of data.

Define the categories for the use cases and find all the inputs needs by every user inside the country it is complex. It is useful but not efficient. About all of that this document becomes to

tool and not in an annex or deliverable document. This document it is not useful so that can't be find it in annex.

5.4. Gaps

5.4.1. Formant description

Based on the deliverables of the technological work packages, gaps for harmonisation have been identified in different areas related to the project tasks.

The identification on gaps at the technological deliverables is located in a harmonization framework capable of supporting given technological solutions, developed and real use case driven implemented for first responders. All of that identified gaps are identified considering a cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical approach.

5.4.2. Current status M12

Technology work packages (WP4, WP5 & WP6) based on prior identification of gaps have identified a number of gaps.

A first version of the gaps has now been produced. These gaps are categorised in each of the work packages and their tasks and these mark their scope. In the coming months work will continue on these gaps in order to make a final delivery of these in the last stage of the project.

5.4.3. Gaps WP4

The WP4 (Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses) has the following scope:

- The utilisation of all available equipment at disaster situations for successful actuation with particular emphasis the health support wearable devices to monitor and analyse both patients and emergency response staff
- Enable the establishment of trusted communications for sharing operational information in a multi-domain environment of stakeholders
- The setting up of a mobile C&C to put in place both operational decision-making and action planning in a coordinated way
- Enable the deployment of connected and autonomous driving enablers to support the disaster response actuation

The above scope corresponds to sections the above scope corresponds to sections and number of gaps identified in each one.

- 4.1 First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units. N° of gaps:11
- 4.2 Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals. N° of gaps: 43
- 4.3 Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies. N° of gaps: 47
- 4.4 The digitalization on first aid actuations. N° of gaps: 14
- 4.5 Instrumentation and health support wearables devices. N° of gaps: 29

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D4.2.

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.1-1	Common operation picture (COP)		
G4.1-1a	Accurate and live weather data	Open-source data	Weather information is important in all SAR operations. Temperature, precipitation, wind speed and direction are common for all cases. Other data such as humidity, barometric data, wave high and so is important I some cases.
G4.1-1b	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure	Map information as well as pictures	In a large-scale disaster situation like earthquakes, floodings or fires, the terrain affected will change. Roads may have disappeared, or rivers have new courses. To give as effective disaster relief as possible, it is essential for the first responders to have an updated and accurate map. This has traditionally been done with aircrafts and satellites. If the first responder teams have access to drones, they can scan the area based on their own needs and can get an accurate picture of the situation for their tasks: if it is firefighting, evacuation, or logistical support.
G4.1-2	Safety for first responders		One of the first principles is own (responder) safety. Especially in case of first-line responders who are facing unknown situation. In case of CBRN incident, the first thing to consider after the presence of hazardous materials is suspected or confirmed at the scene, is to remember to prioritise own personal safety so responder can do the job without becoming a casualty. Use caution and keep a safe distance to avoid exposure own self and by avoiding unnecessary contact with casualties, people and surfaces that may have been contaminated.
G4.1-2a	Tracking of personnel and casualties	Position	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically. This information has several possible benefits, such as area monitoring for better understanding of what areas have been searched (historic track data), to provide assistance to personnel in congested areas or inside buildings in order to find quickest and/or safest way to injured people for medical aid and evacuation or to

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			get them to safe areas if the situation deteriorate.
G4.1-2b	Safe work environment for first responder personnel	Information on toxicity, radioactivity and similar challenges	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.
G4.1-3	Logistical support		
G4.1-3a	Build ad hoc communication grids	Physical units are placed out in the disaster area to re-establish communication	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of data files and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.
G4.1-3b	Distribution of equipment	Transport of needed equipment to first responders	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, like bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding under normal condition but in a disaster area with destroyed roads and inaccessible areas this will become a challenge. In recent years is it developed several unmanned vehicles with the purpose to transport goods. For the first leg, from main storage areas, UGVs can transport goods and equipment to the forward operation bases (FOB). From FOB, a UAV can take small parcels to the first responders in the field. Also, at sea, the possibility exists to use USV as transport units from shore to disaster area and use UAV to distribute the parcels to the different vessels operating in the areas.
G4.1-3c	Supply energy and charging capabilities	All electrically driven units need charging close to the operation area	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother" vehicles

Identification of Gaps			
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
G4.1-4	Conduct search and relief missions		Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 1 - Gaps from First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-1	Communication coverage and availability	Professional experience	Current technologies used for communication present coverage limitations, especially in rural areas. This is a drawback for emergency agencies that rely in specific technologies.
G4.2-2	Network recovering in case of disaster	Professional experience and Survey	Network architecture deployed during multiple casualty emergencies may not have adequate mechanisms to recover telecommunications services.
G4.2-3	Limited coverage ranges in communications devices	Professional experience and Survey	Due to the heterogeneity of the devices, many of which are limited in performance, data transmissions are made over short distances.
G4.2-4	Bandwidth appropriate to the level of coverage	Literature	The types of use cases in a disaster response scenario—sharing high resolution GIS maps, streaming video, and large amounts of voice communication—necessitate high-bandwidth and low- latency connections.
G4.2-5	Dynamic device selection based on transmission preference	Literature	Particularly in disaster events, networks in affected areas typically receive very high volumes of incoming calls and data. A limiting factor is concurrency with large numbers of devices communicating simultaneously.
G4.2-6	Lack of secure communications	Survey	Certain emergency services do not use secure communications for sensitive data transmission.
G4.2-7	Lack of communications security monitoring	Survey	Most network architectures deployed in emergencies do not have network monitoring systems capable of detecting threats or anomalies.
G4.2-8	Most communication technologies are not interoperable	Professional experience and Surveys	Technologies used nowadays in emergency scenarios work insulated from the rest.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-9	Lack of strategies to determine the best technology based on security constraints	Professional experience	There are no regulations or guidelines for selecting the most suitable communication technology or protocols based on security requirements.
G4.2-10	There are no strict guidelines for backup plans	Surveys	There is a lack of regulations that enforce emergency institutions to implement backup plans
G4.2-11	There are no contingency plans at EU level for data restoration	Professional experience	In case of data loss, there are no clear guidelines on how to proceed.
G4.2-12	Lack of redundancy systems and services in the event of failure or catastrophe	Professional experience	In the event of an emergency affecting the proposed systems, there are no identical systems to make up for this shortcoming.
G4.2-13	Ad hoc network coverage	Literature	As multiple devices, and thus technologies, will be involved in the emergency actuations, the coverage provided by ad hoc deployment could not include all of them.
G4.2-14	Personal Data	Literature	As the data related with emergency actuations will likely be personal and sensible data, it is possible that not all the confidentiality requirements will be satisfied.
G4.2-15	Accurate service provisioning	Literature	Due to the variability of the first aid actuations, the service provisioning might be inaccurate, leading to malfunctions and security breaches.
G4.2-16	Ad hoc network scope	Professional experience	Ad hoc emergency services networks are often developed at regional, local or even agency level in EU countries (e.g., in Spain), which runs counter to the interoperability of systems and services in emergency response.
G4.2-17	Inadequate reliability of the 2G, 3G or 4G network in disasters	Literature	2G, 3G or 4G are the most widely used alternative to TETRA radio systems by the emergency services, especially in terms of data transmission. But reality shown that their capacity and availability is very limited in mass casualty incidents, where these networks often have collapsed within first minutes.
G4.2-18	Negative burden of low frequency of use and legacy solutions	Professional experience	The networks used by the Emergency Services are generally adequate for their usual activity and will have involved a significant investment over time. Large new investments in infrastructure or devices with no obvious day-to-day impact, but only for infrequent

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			incidents such as MCI, is an unattractive prospect for their managers.
G4.2-19	Consolidated reported information	Literature	Creation of communication agreements. Development of message structures. Identification of profiles, roles and protocols.
G4.2-20	Asymmetric information flow	Professional experience	In the first moments of the disaster, the avalanche of information coming from the incident site can overwhelm the coordinating centre's ability to receive and process it.
G4.2-21	Line saturation	Professional experience	The use of shared technologies (e.g., mobile network, fixed telephone network) may be saturated not only by the personnel involved in the disaster, but also by other incidental or non-participants in the disaster. Each technology has certain limits for handling concurrent calls.
G4.2-22	Terminals that are difficult to operate in disaster situations	Professional experience	Terminals commonly used by emergency services provide a service adapted to a use that can be excessively complicated in the event of disasters, requiring many operations to initiate communication, and interruptions or disruptions that make communication difficult.
G4.2-23	Minimum acceptable technology requirements	Professional experience	Determine minimum technological characteristics to guarantee optimal service level in emergency and disaster situations.
G4.2-24	Local data collection	Professional experience	Explore new sensors data networks (e.g., Lora) devices to collect local data.
G4.2-25	FR and Victims data	Professional experience	Explore new devices to collect First responder and victims' data.
G4.2-26	TETRA coms	Literature	Coverage of TETRA data do not uniform across the users.
G4.2-27	Coms range extension	Professional experience	Use of relay nodes to extend the RF communications coverage of or to overcome Line of sight Communications limitations.
G4.2-28	Data rates	Literature	Different networks data rates impact quality of the data channelling through networks.
G4.2-29	Data latency	Literature	Different networks latency impact quality of the data channelling through networks.
G4.2-30	Data Priority	Literature	In a limited bandwidth communications context, the absence of operational data priority impacts the decision-making process and managing of critical situation.

Identification of gaps			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-31	Data protocols	Literature	Federated data may not be transmitted to different network if data protocols are not supported.
G4.2-32	IP network layer	Literature	Not all communication devices or networks support IP layer as a standard.
G4.2-33	Data shared	Professional experience	Different entities codify its data communication using different data protocols
G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Professional experience	Emergency events often face multiple communications issues, such as communication connectivity, constraints, networks unavailability, congestion, etc.
G4.2-35	Data cluster	Professional experience	As the volume of information and data increases in large scale incidents, the data loss and recover, as well as the data sharing latencies and delays may impact the overall performance of the system.
G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	Professional experience	In emergency situation, a federated solution of applications/functions may be unavailable in case of communication / connectivity loss.
G4.2-37	Blockchain redundancy	Professional experience	Operational redundancy required redundancy may not jeopardize the system security.
G4.2-38	Share health data	Literature	Use a common data protocol / standard to share health data.
G4.2-39	Querying data	Literature and professional experience	Query different data sources in a common, scalable and efficient way.
G4-2-40	System fragility due to interdependencies	Professional experience	Systems that consist of interdependent services may be face loss of functionalities even if one support service (dependency) fails.
G4.2-41	Legal and regulatory constraints	Literature and professional experience	There is a lack of protocols or legal aspects for a group of countries facing the same emergency.
G4.2-42	No institutional set-up for communications during emergencies	Professional experience	Current Government agencies and the private sector have an insufficient capacity to deal emergencies with different technical options.
G4.2-43	Constraints with cross-boundary movement of communications	Professional experience	Lack of planned management or coordination, as well as poor preparedness among international organizations.

Table 2 - Gaps from Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminal

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-1	No real-time information exchange	Professional Experience	Emergency services coordination require near real-time inputs in order to avoid delays. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-2	Lack of sensory & communications integrations	Survey	Data-intensive operative environment is poorly integrated. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-3	Insufficient the capacity of Coalition cooperation	Literature	C2 overall design purpose should accomplish coalition fulfilment. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-4	Leverage logistics databases information	Literature	The aim is to function as a cross-cutting emergency system while maintaining current tools. Tools such as the GIS have to be fed with external data. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
G4.3-5	Delays and disconnecting	Survey	Many times, the C2 Commander is not able to take decisions due to delays and disconnecting. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-6	Lack of C2 communication means in rural areas	Professional Experience	Prevent any comms failure due to terrain characteristics in rural areas. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-7	Disunities COP	Professional Experience	Currently there is not a common COP of the situation. Each agency has their own events and deploy their resources in function their overview. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
G4.3-8	Situational awareness uncompleted set of information	Professional Experience	Missing set of essential information. To take advantage of the situation such as n° of tracking, n° of victims, responders, NO-GO zones and type of responders are required. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-9	Non harmonisation of graphics symbols, views, and representations	Professional Experience	No global symbols. Add difficulties if the information is shared by third parties. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-10	Short accuracy for network transmitter	Professional Experience	Extend the range of network coverage to communicate with the 112-emergency coordination centre. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-11	Enhance time response signal between Emergency Vehicles – Emergency Operator in GIS	Survey	The geolocation signal of emergency vehicles deployed in GIS is too slow. Real-time communications prevent issues related to navigated rescuers by operator. <i>Technological</i>

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-12	Video display (CCTV) no integrated functionalities	Professional Experience	CCTV Integration with external cameras. Integrations with third party SW. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-13	Meeting points	Survey	Map out the meeting points. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-14	Type of dangerous substance	Survey	Specify the types of hazardous substances to tailor deployment and mitigate negative effects. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-15	Endangered areas	Survey	Overprotecting sensitive natural areas. It can cause irreparable damage to the ecosystem. <i>Procedural and Cross-border</i>
G4.3-16	Contact to incident commander or command post chief	Professional Experience	Communications improvements with Command Post Chief. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-17	Information area coverage by drones	Professional experience	Improve the situational awareness of large areas events, to overcome the lack of aerial information and multiple sensors capacity.
G4.3-18	Improved imagery ground resolution	Professional experience	Have a high Ground imagery sensors data resolution is critical resource to manage the situation, in particular detection of hot spots.
G4.3-19	Drones' data protocols	Professional experience	Imagery quality for high quality real-time data transmission requires high bandwidth and proper metadata to enable ground applications exploitation from multiple drones' providers.
G4.3-20	Nigh data gathering	Professional experience + legislation	Aviation, including drones, have limited flying condition in night condition, from sunset to sunrise, in fire events, due to safety issues. Improved aerial coordination capability is required to plan night operations.
G4.3-21	Airspace management tools	Professional experience + Regulation	With an increased number of flying drones over the operational theatre, there is a need to improve the air traffic management capability, deconflicting flight areas, establish aerial fences, and comply with safety, privacy, and air flying rules.
G4.3-22	Drones RF management tools	Professional experience	The increased number of RF communication used in MCI, including many drones operating in the same frequencies, may generated communication collision and/or loss of communication with some assets.
G4.3-23	Development of a standardised electronic triage system for the facilitation and	Literature	There is a need for a standardised system that allows for quick triage procedures to limit response times and increase situation awareness.

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	improvement of logistics management and accomplishment		
G4.3-24	Standardisation of systems for an automated management of resources e.g., for the assignment of resources to tasks and missions	Literature	There is a need for standardised system to be used for the management of resources e.g., geolocation of personnel and vehicles, tasks assigned to the different resources.
G4.3-25	Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data	Literature	Standardisation for the compliance of sensitive data with legislations for the protection of personal data is required.
G4.3-26	Triage procedures	Professional experience	As no standard exists on who provides first phase triage (medical personnel only or and others), the initial identification of a victim, in most cases containing non-medical or other personal sensitive data, photos included, must be allowed using multi-colour bracelets supporting one form pf electronic tagging available (RF, 3DCode, NFT etc). Initiation and first entry of available data has to be recorded in a secured way (strongly recommended in blockchain). Other important information related with the victim, such as location, time of triage/initiation, first-responder id etc is captured from first responder's smart phone or tablet recording the victim.
G4.3-27	Clocks synchronization	Professional experience	Different manual or computerized systems use different clock setting methods to synchronize. As the VALKYRIES system must link different federated systems all logging transactions or metadata in a common structure (blockchain logging), clocks synchronizations should be adapted through this function
G4.3-28	The legacy of solutions for C2	Professional experience	C2 solutions have been developed largely at the agency level, highly focused on their own needs and heavily conditioned by their own development or procurement capabilities, which detracts from their effectiveness and works against accessibility and interoperability

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			between first responders in different agencies or territories.
G4.3-29	The weight of habit	Professional experience	Unified C2 solutions developed at regional or national level are sometimes less used than would be possible because they involve incident commanders moving away from their own agency tools with which they are familiar, and in situations where stress and demands are higher.
G4.3-30	Confidentiality versus information sharing	Professional experience	The need to ensure the security of information transmission and the confidentiality of the transmitted data itself, especially in relation to emergency medical services, has sometimes worked against the development of interoperable C2 and decision support solutions, as well as facilitating the exchange of information. Information sharing.
G4.3-31	Need for specific functionalities to meet specific needs	Professional experience	The critical information and decision criteria are indeed different in day-to-day situations managed by an Emergency Medical Service compared to a multi-casualty incident. This means that the solutions developed for day-to-day EMS C2, and decision making are often not suitable for disaster medical management, requiring specific new functionalities.
G4.3-32	Lack of social media analysis on emergency scenarios	Professional experience	There is an absence of guidelines and regulations offering recommendations for crawling social media data for analysing emergency situations.
G4.3-33	Lack of clear guidelines for selecting data crawling tools	Professional experience	There is a need at EU level for providing clear guidelines indicating which tools are more suitable for crawling social media for emergency scenarios.
G4.3-34	Cross border trace of data sharing authorization	Professional experience	Data shared among countries are subjected do international agreements and authorization which, and the identification of which data is allowed to be shared at each moment is required.
G4.3-35	Victim's advance information	Professional experience	The number of victims, its status and health conditions must be matched with the hospital medical capability and reported to the specific destination medical facility. There is no point if sharing all the data of victims to medical facilities that are will not receive the victims. It will only generate noise.

Identification of gaps			
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-36	Victims' health / historical data	Professional experience	Absence of the medical historical data of victims can limit the medical procedures. The victim's historical data can be directly assessed by the medical facility, but the information of the victim identification and authorization prior to its arrival to thaw medical facility may delays the medical response.
G4.3-37	Victims' data traceability	Professional experience	Improve the Victims traceability and tracking while in the response process to avoid victim loss in the transportation process, or loss of victim's awareness.
G4.3-38	FR Follow-up	Professional Experience	Last know position of FR and trace its position provides a valuable resource management capability.
G4.3-39	External data sources	Professional Experience	There are many potential external sources of information that can be integrated in the system, providing additional valuable data.
G4.3-40	Social media	Professional Experience	Social media data and information usability in C2 systems requires a careful filtering and validation to avoid misinformation and data noise.
G4.3-41	Wide use of sensors	Professional Experience	There is a wide range of new sensors and protocol, easy to deploy that can provide valuable field data, and are not currently exploited.
G4.3-42	Traceability of victims	Personal experience	In MCIs, victims, especially unconscious ones, maybe transferred to a medical facility without their families being notified, rendering their tracking extremely difficult both for the families and the relevant authorities as well.
G4.3-43	Identification of dangerous zones	Professional experience	The identification of dangerous zones varies across countries and organisations.
G4.3-44	Identification of relevant locations	Professional experience	Organisations use different technological solutions to identify relevant locations.
G4.3-45	No widespread use of decision support applications	Professional experience	The use of decision support applications is not widespread in the emergency services.
G4.3-46	Standardization of operating procedures	Professional experience	The need to update current operating procedures with new standards, equipment and devices is detected.
G4.3-47	New command and control standards	Professional experience	Necessary review of command-and-control standards.

Table 3- Gaps from Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies.

Identification of gaps			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-1	Lack of iconographic standard	Professional experience	It is required to standardize the iconographic representation used by the organizations during the first aid actuations.
G4.4-2	Iconographic discrepancies	Professional experience	It is common than the signalling employed during emergency actuations will present usage discrepancies between nations/organizations.
G4.4-3	Language barrier	Literature	Currently, every nation uses its language in emergency communications, hindering the information sharing.
G4.4-4	Data Normalization	Professional experience	As multiple digitalization instances should be interconnected, such as DTAs and Static models, the data should be normalized or standardized in a common language.
G4.4-5	Graphical capabilities	Professional experience	Although the digital modelling does not require too much computing nor graphical capabilities, not all the systems currently involved during first aid actuations might be able to support its representation.
G4.4-6	Continuous communication	Literature	As the digital representation should be a faithful representation of the emergency actuations, the information should be constantly updated.
G4.4-7	Ad-hoc network coverage	Literature	The digitalization of first aid actuation poses as a challenge itself, and the integration with suboptimal networks might be a hard challenge that should be addressed during ad-hoc deployments during emergency actuations.
G4.4-8	Neglecting to facilitate the work of the first responder leads to the failure of proposals.	Professional experience	Digitalization solutions for EMS intervention in multiple casualty situations do not always identify the main objective of making the work of first responders easier in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual. This reduces the chances of success.
G4.4-9	Reliability and usability in extreme conditions, a necessity in disaster response.	Professional experience	The reliability and usability of electronic devices in extreme conditions is very high nowadays, but there are specific conditions in disaster intervention that still need to be improved: behaviour in rain or blood, usability with stained gloves, use in low visibility conditions, excessive brightness or radical contrasts, etc.
G4.4-10	Generational digital divide in healthcare	Literature	Despite technological advances and growth of social demand to incorporate them into daily clinical practice, the level of implementation

Identification of gaps			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			of digital innovation in the healthcare sector is still limited and slow, partly due to the generational digital divide.
G4.4-11	Excessive use of non-digital communications	Professional experience	Most emergency services in Europe use voice as their primary means of communication. Moreover, this use is sometimes not very brief and not very protocolled.
G4.4-12	Digitization increases the workload of first responders.	Professional experience	Related to G4.4-8. Many digital technologies currently used in emergency services are not useful for multiple casualty care because they require a lot of work, rather than freeing up first responders to deal with casualty care.
G4.4-13	Lack of uses of AI-based systems	Survey	Currently there are no artificial intelligence-based systems for support in emergency situations.
G4.4-14	Lack of training systems	Survey	Currently, no gamification-based techniques are used for RF training.

Table 4 - Gaps from the digitalization on first aid actuations.

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-1	Lack of user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently, emergency incident management systems do not have methods for automatic tracking of both users and FRs in emergency incidents.
G4.5-2	Dependence of coverage on user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently systems are not adapted to different needs depending on the coverage available.
G4.5-3	Lack of user identification	Professional experience - Survey	There are currently no devices that allow for the identification of users in emergency scenarios.
G4.5-4	Current commercial devices do not have the necessary technologies.	Personal experience	Current commercial devices are severely limited in terms of the communication technologies available to them.
G4.5-5	Inaccessibility to the firmware of the devices.	Literature review	Modification of the firmware that is built into commercial devices is either very costly or impossible, so it cannot be adapted to the requested needs.
G4.5-6	Reduced device battery life	Literature review	The battery life of devices can be greatly reduced when, depending on the technology they incorporate and how they are used.
G4.5-7	Lack of use of wearable devices for first triage	Professional experience	Wearable devices are not currently used to assign a first triage to patients in an emergency.

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-8	Lack of devices to measure health status continuously in patients.	Professional experience	Currently no systems are used to monitor the different bio-signals of a patient and define the severity of the patient automatically.
G4.5-9	Different communication systems between First Responders	Professional experience	At present different agencies use different communication systems (VHF, mobile phone, TETRA) which may have signal problems, and which often do not “talk” to each other.
G4.5-10	No common communication standard between different countries	Professional experience	Even when, within the same country, there is a single strategy for communication between agencies in emergencies this standard is hardly ever extended beyond national borders
G4.5-11	Difficult to report a personal threat	Professional experience	The diffusion of solutions that make it possible to transmit requests for help or autonomously report dangerous situations of the FRs (e.g., panic buttons on radio equipment or position sensor) is still not widespread. In addition to this, the information is almost always transmitted to the system by voice over local networks
G4.5-12	Not immediate detection and reporting hazards during crisis response	Professional experience	The use of personal sensors is often limited to CO and low O2 detection. Sensors sensitive to different substances and explosimeters are often hand-held devices. Wearables that allow a personal hazard warning to be sent are still uncommon.
G4.5-13	Dissemination of safety and security information to FRs	Professional experience	Transmission of safety- and security-related information is almost always via voice over local radio networks
G4.5-14	Inaccurate Disaster Fatality Identification	Professional experience	Only in some realities are images of the find scene captured, usually by camera, without the ability to transmit and store them quickly and safely. In addition, much other information is not detected (e.g., GPS location).
G4.5-15	Problems related to mortuary laws	Professional experience - literature	There are no shared DVI procedures between different countries. There is no clear guidance on how to make a presumptive identification already at an MCI site. The use of technological aids in the field is minimized
G4.5-16	Lack of validated protocols for e-triage	Literature	Triage protocols for MCI based on the parameters that can be monitored by the sensors currently integrated in wearables, which are still limited, have not yet been validated.
G4.5-17	Logistical constraints	Professional experience	To be effective in an MCI, wearable devices for instrumentation and healthcare support need to

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			be in place at the scene in the first moments of the accident. The logistics of ensuring this are complex, especially in widely dispersed emergency medical services. Conventional EMS vehicles, primarily ambulances, often have significant space constraints that leave little room for additional equipment.
G4.5-18	Relevance of investment in wearable technology in MCI	Professional experience	The investment in the development or acquisition of wearables and communication solutions for the location, traceability, or e-triage of victims in an MCI is considerable in large emergency medical services, being resources with a relatively low frequency of use compared to other resources destined for daily activity. Together with the fact that it does not lead to direct cost savings, it is often unattractive to the healthcare manager.
G4.5-19	Investing in acquisition may not be the best option.	Professional experience	Due to the accelerated rate of innovation in these devices, an eventual investment in procurement may quickly make these devices technologically outdated.
G4.5-20	Unified User roles	Professional experience	Each application and entity have its organizational structure, roles and accesses/permissions for their users. Sharing data in a non-coherent federation role structure can generate loss of trust and accountability.
G4.5-21	D2D communications integration	Professional experience	There is no global standard to easily integrate D2D communications assets and its data into a federated network.
G4.5-22	Victims monitor data	Professional experience	Critical data on the health status of victims are not available for medical services to prepare their response.
G4.5-23	Telemedicine	Professional experience	In fast development and large events nonskilled personnel may provide minimal assistance to victims in life threatening situation, where a remote guidance on how to provide minimal life support actions could save life. A Telemedicine service is required to provide this support.
G4.5-24	Cost of modern technology equipment	Professional experience	Modern technological equipment, especially devices aimed for victims, may be too costly to purchase in adequate quantities, even for MCIs with relatively low numbers of victims, leading FR agencies to have limited resources for when a crisis strikes.
G4.5-25	Wearables for most critically ill patients.	Professional experience	They may not be suitable for the most critically ill patients in whom injuries may make it

Identification of gaps			
Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			difficult or impossible to place and take vital signs.
G4.5-26	Lack of standardization of the functionalities of wearables	Literature	Wearable devices have functionalities such as heart rate, blood oxygen level, but we do not know how reliable they are.
G4.5-27	Lack of functionalities according to medical regulations	Literature	The information provided by the wearables should be medical regulations, so that it can be interpreted by any doctor.
G4.5-28	First responders not available for wearables	Literature	In order to protect first responders through wearables, it is necessary to provide them with these devices.
G4.5-29	Lack of a global regulation regarding the working conditions of first responders.	Literature	Wearable devices have functionalities such as stress level, sleep hours which can help to control your physical and mental state.

Table 5 - Gaps from Instrumentation and health support wearables devices

5.4.4. Gaps WP5

The WP5 (Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses) has the scope of provide an information framework of the common EU operational plans and procedures.

The search for gaps and opportunities will lead to the production of guidelines and harmonisation recommendations for practices and operational procedures for facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between actors in the first aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters.

This WP5 will facilitate the understanding of the complex map of practises and operative procedures in aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters, by surveying, studying and analysing the common practices, reconnaissance, triage and care of victims, crisis response planning, maintenance, logistics, C&C operations, development of a Common Operational Picture and alerting/warning.

The above scope corresponds to sections and number of gaps identified in each one.

In this WP5, tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.4 have been divided in order to correctly categorise the identified gaps.

- 5.1.1 Crisis response planning. N° of gaps: 7
- 5.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage. N° of gaps: 14
- 5.2.1 Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment. N° of gaps: 9
- 5.2.2 Others maintenance, logistics and deployment. N° of gaps: 5
- 5.3 Command and control and support to operational decision-making. N° of gaps: 19
- 5.4.1 Common Operational Picture. N° of gaps: 15
- 5.4.2 Alert and warning. N° of gaps: 9

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D5.2.

Identification of gaps			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.1-1	Lack of standardisation of terms and symbols for a common interpretation of data and a common operational picture	LITERATURE	There is no standardised glossary of terms, semantic representations or symbols sufficiently comprehensive to serve at EU level as a reference for planning, development, communications or operational actions in relation to MCIs and disasters.
G5.1.1-2	Following of Guidelines of EU Civil Protection	SURVEY	Harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines is not achievable due to G1 and G1 above
G5.1.1-3	Lack of regulatory harmonisation between countries in disaster planning and response	SURVEY	Lack of harmonization between the law of different territories in relation to MCI and disaster planning or response.
G5.1.1-4	Inconsistency of crisis response plans	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In Mass Casualty Incidents are all crisis response plans inconsistent between all involved emergency agencies. Most of the emergency plans were created but have not been updated many years. Plans are outdated and do not reflect nowadays situation.
G5.1.1-5	Lack of dissemination of emergency plans	SURVEY	Lack of implementation of civil protection plans: lack of dissemination, education of the population, education and training of those involved and development of operational procedures for action groups.
G5.1.1-6	Rescue Plans Activation Gap	LITERATURE	As cross-border incidents might influence the involved countries unproportionally to their criteria, the activation of Crisis Management Rescue Plans as per their criteria might not signal the need for C2 handling from both countries' emergency operations centres
G5.1.1-7	Roles definition Gaps	LITERATURE	Different "role definitions" and privileges accessing data are in place between different federated systems. Such systems are tuned to support operations, workflows and procedure from such roles accordingly. Their gaps might create huge problems in data exchange between federated systems if a centralized

Identification of gaps			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			approach is in force, resulting to non-operational systems

Table 6 - Gaps from crisis response planning

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-1	Different EMS structure and composition	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The structure and composition of the Emergency Services varies considerably from country to country or region to region, which is a factor favouring a great diversity in chains of command and operational procedures.
G5.1.2-2	Ununified procedures	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In each country, different types of actors as first responders, military and civilians, are involved with completely different approach as per their logistics and/or their C2, following operational procedures completely different between countries. Thus, their harmonization on common procedures is difficult to impossible.
G5.1.2-3	Different professional competencies among first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The capacity to administer specific medical care at the scene of a disaster varies according to the professional profiles deployed at the scene of the emergency and the professional competencies established by law in each country, e.g., presence or absence of physicians.
G5.1.2-4	Lack of first responders' knowledge and preparation	LITERATURE	The lack of preparedness of responders sometimes results in inadequate knowledge of procedures, access, use of PPE and safety measures, etc., which compromises the disaster response.
G5.1.2-5	Lack of common training and certification	SURVEY	There is no common training and certification at first responder level (EMS & Fire Service) in first aid. In some European countries for example the fire brigade can give first aid interventions/manoeuvres etc while in others not.
G5.1.2-6	Non-standardised zoning	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Zoning is essential for organising the response to the accident on the scene. However, the definition of working zones differs between different agencies, in each case generally according to the specific needs of the institutions: security, firefighting and rescue, health care.

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-7	Ambulances tracking and recording	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The vehicles arrive from different areas, not all ambulances have a GPS system that speaks to each other.
G5.1.2-8	Non-standardised victim registration and affiliation information	LITERATURE	Victim registration and affiliation: information and the procedure of registering and exchanging victim's information is not unified, and traceability is not guaranteed in cross-border incidents or where different agencies work together.
G5.1.2-9	Different triage standards and practices in use within countries between different first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Not harmonized procedures in first triage and evacuation. First responders are unclear who is responsible for this task. In many EU countries these procedures vary. Detailed triage and first medical support to victims or short triage and fast evacuation - this is also challenging issue. In some countries, trained firefighters, coast guards or volunteers provide first stage triage, prior to the handling of the victim to EMS, in others not. The harmonization in cross-border incidents is difficult to impossible, mainly for victims with ethnics or citizenship that differs to the country's agent that rescued.
G5.1.2-10	Non-standardised victim priority tagging	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Victim tagging: tapes, triage cards, wearables... The alphanumeric or colour codes that make the priority of victims visible are not completely unified.
G5.1.2-11	Victim's clinical information	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Lack of clinical information based on patient conditions
G5.1.2-12	Non-consensual criteria for determining means and destination of transfer	LITERATURE	Evacuation and transfer: There are no agreed recommendations for deciding the means of evacuation in MCI, which must be timely and appropriate to ensure quality care, but taking into account the real availability of resources in each case.
G5.1.2-13	Limited involvement of many hospital facilities in MCI and disaster	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Evacuation and transfer: in many cases the involvement of hospitals in the response to external MCIs is somewhat passive, limited to updating their capabilities at the request of the command centre in charge of the incident.

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	response planning		
G5.1.2-14	Unedified standards for debriefing and evaluation	SURVEY	Standards and procedures between emergency agencies for debriefing and evaluation are not unified and connected

Table 7 - Gaps from reconnaissance and triage

Identification of gaps			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.1-1	Communication needs	SURVEY	Experiencing communication difficulties between the other various technical actors
G5.2.1-2	Outdated technology and system	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In common - most emergency agencies (Firefighters, EMS,...) face the problem that technology and systems are outdated
G5.2.1-3	Lack of portability	LITERATURE	The lack of portability force users of one service to learn the other service's application, or for the application and hardware system to integrate with the larger system
G5.2.1-4	Excessive use of radio communication	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Radio networks with voice information transmission are widely used, but have limited data transmission capacity, which is insufficient to build a common operational picture for disaster assessment and decision-making. In general the first responder are provided with radio communication, which means that they become saturated and errors can be made in the transmission of message
G5.2.1-5	Use of non-optimal alternative communication channels in MCI	LITERATURE	Given the limitations of radio networks, the alternative use of mobile and fixed telephone networks for strategic and operational communications makes it difficult to exchange information with other responders in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.1-6	Usage of different software within emergency services	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Not all emergency services use the same software - therefore the communication between operators within the system could lead to losing some important information

Identification of gaps			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			about the whole incident or particular part of it.
G5.2.1-7	Limited use of e-health options in MCI and disasters	LITERATURE	Limited use of e-health technologies, which are currently revolutionising standard healthcare, in MCI and disaster response.
G5.2.1-8	Operating procedures conditioned by obsolete ICTs	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The obsolete communication systems available to some emergency services condition their own operational procedures, forcing them to devote excessive efforts and resources to these purposes, to the detriment of the effectiveness of victim care.
G5.2.1-9	Recording information sometimes make it difficult for first responders to do their job.	LITERATURE	The need to enter information into the C2 system by voice or by manual typing of data places a significant burden on first responders and limits the fluidity and even accuracy of the data.

Table 8 - Gaps from communication maintenance, logistics and deployment

Identification of gaps			
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.2-1	Lack of standardisation of logistical procedures	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Logistics and health deployment procedures are not standardised in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.2-2	Lack of inter-agency logistics procedures	SURVEY	There are no unified inter-agency crisis procedures for logistics, maintenance and deployment.
G5.2.2-3	Insufficient logistics management tools at the national level	LITERATURE	There is a good interlocking of logistics managed by the EU and the UN, but there are deficiencies in the tools to support pre-disaster logistics planning in the different countries.
G5.2.2-4	Variability in logistics resources for disaster response.	SURVEY	The availability of certain deployment support elements such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to set up an advanced medical post is inconsistent.

Identification of gaps			
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.2-5	Insufficient and non-standardised training in logistics applied to MCI and disasters	SURVEY	Despite EU recommendations for standardised formal education in humanitarian logistics, specialised training needs to be coordinated for each country.

Table 9 - Gaps from others maintenance, logistics and deployment

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-1	Not a unique emergency operations centre operating in all countries	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In most cases, different C2 non-compatible emergency operations centres operate even within the same country to support/manage police, health or firefighters/first responders. As so, different "operational view" is available to each C2, resulting to mismanagement or not proper execution of the rescue plan. The same stands for cross-border incidents
G5.3.1-2	Different crisis emergency operation's centre locations	SURVEY	For Medical and non-medical organizations, the crisis emergency operations centres (EOC) are located in different places. It could be an issue because currently there are limited resources in terms of communication and may difficult decision-making management task by Command Post Leaders.
G5.3.1-3	Lack of integration of certain emergency services in the emergency operations centre.	SURVEY	In some countries, emergency operations centres do not integrate all emergency services, which can delay the provision of incident information and make coordination between services difficult.
G5.3.1-4	Municipality supportive agents excluded from C2	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	During disasters, municipalities or cities are engaged in first respond agents, mainly as logistics or supporting agents. In some countries they are included with such roles in emergency plans, in others not. There is a gap that need to be faced as municipality's local C2s usually are not included or communicate properly with C2
G5.3.1-5	Heterogeneous emergency systems in different territories	LITERATURE	EU countries have a similar crisis management system but the structure and composition of their EMSs are different, with command or operational coordination roles differing more or less substantially from each other. This hampers the homogeneity of procedures, inter-agency dialogue and the effective exchange of information.

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-6	Different criteria for assigning roles in different territories	LITERATURE	Civil Protection recommendations on planning establish in a more or less homogeneous way the tasks to be attended to and the roles to be established to ensure an adequate response to the disaster. But these roles are not always assigned to the same services in the different plans.
G5.3.1-7	Linear plans and positive control not thriving in complex situations	LITERATURE	Current C2 Systems are not flexible in multidisciplinary environments and highly susceptible to changes due to complex situations.
G5.3.1-8	Difference in overall incident command in the emergency operations centre.	SURVEY	There are differences regarding overall incident command at the emergency operations centre in the response to an MCI or disaster: it may be firefighters or civil protection.
G5.3.1-9	Difference in overall incident command at the scene.	SURVEY	There is a lot of variability in relation to which agency has overall on-scene command in the response to an MCI or disaster.
G5.3.1-10	Difference in hazard control and zoning command	SURVEY	The agency responsible for hazard control and zoning may be firefighters, civil protection or even police, depending on different plans and territories.
G5.3.1-11	Difference in rescue command	SURVEY	There is variability in who has overall on-scene rescue command in response to an MCI or disaster: it can be firefighters, EMS, or even some police units (e.g. mountain group of the Guardia Civil in Spain).
G5.3.1-12	Complexity of C2 information flows	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The flow of both operational and command and control information with the current systems that support it is often too complex, leading to slowdowns and increased likelihood of errors.
G5.3.1-13	Legacy C2 applications	SURVEY	In common - outdated technology and systems
G5.3.1-14	Interoperability C2	SURVEY	Interoperability issues. Integrated informational and GIS systems that will interact with all stakeholders are not configured and deployed.

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-15	Communication delays among the interveners.	LITERATURE	There are delays among the interveners in the process of information acquisition, communication and decision-making.
G5.3.1-16	Lost Communications and their logs	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	As there is not any existing common logging system of communications, messages or transactions between operators of the same C2, it is likely that crucial data can be lost, especially in cases where auditing is required to support victim cases in courts.
G5.3.1-17	Time synchronization gap	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Logging of events or transactions with no time synchronization might create problems in auditing procedures
G5.3.1-18	Lack of C2 education and training	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Joint workflows between C2 systems are not standardised and often require the support of training programmes, which are often insufficient.
G5.3.1-19	Very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2	LITERATURE	The information that is currently recorded in relation to command-and-control decisions or operational actions is very limited, and that which is recorded in real time does not generally associate data that would make it possible to determine the justification, origin, timing, etc. This makes it practically impossible to carry out a complete objective analysis of the incidents in order to obtain useful and contrasted information.

Table 10 - Gaps from command and control and support to operational decision-making

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-1	Legal constraints to interoperability	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	There are legal barriers that substantially constrain interoperability between technologies and information exchange platforms in C2.
G5.4.1-2	Insufficient awareness of information exchange between agencies and territories	SURVEY	Lack of collaboration between agencies of different administrative dependencies, due to political factors or those associated with the organisational culture.

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-3	Need to better understand the needs of other emergency services	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	There is a need to develop a common knowledge base of the different expertise of emergency personnel, from which to understand how the different responders interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.
G5.4.1-4	Differing information needs for decision making	LITERATURE	The EMS first responders shares less information with other responders in MCI and disaster response. Security and firefighters have common information needs.
G5.4.1-5	No consensus on the basic information to be exchanged between agencies or territories.	LITERATURE	There are no common criteria for identifying relevant information, for information exchange or for data analysis in C2. There is no consensus on the basic information that needs to be shared among emergency commanders for decision-making.
G5.4.1-6	No standardised information exchange processes between agencies or territories	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In general terms, there are no standardised specific information-sharing procedures between the commanders of different agencies or different countries in disaster response.
G5.4.1-7	Limited situational awareness	LITERATURE	Limited knowledge of the situation and its scope sometimes leads to delays in sending the necessary emergency teams. Inadequate systems for recording, storing and interpreting data of relevance to C2, leading to delays in decision-making.
G5.4.1-8	Provide a shared data base of situational information/awareness is needed.	LITERATURE	An adequate COP should provide the relevant information shared by all stakeholders, without exceeding the amount of information presented, as for some users it may be irrelevant or lead to over-information.
G5.4.1-9	Unselective information overload	LITERATURE	Information overload complicates decision-making in MCI and disaster response and creates simplified mental models.
G5.4.1-10	Different weather prediction systems between countries	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Weather prediction, influencing both the C2 decisions and the deployment of help to non-victims, are applicable between countries, following in some cases completely different models and algorithms. So critical information (as for example ground humidity, ground

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			temperature, burning material, sea currents etc.) is not available from all weather services, problems might be created in operational decision making. As so, in cross border incidents such incompatibility has to be resolved.
G5.4.1-11	Mission assessments by technological deployments	LITERATURE	C2 Commanders decision-making relies on briefing suggestions by rest of the participants. There are no technological capabilities in order to increase procedures decision-making according to entire joint schemes of manoeuvre.
G5.4.1-12	Advanced visualization techniques required	LITERATURE	Currently, tools that allow for a common visualisation of the emergency are scarce and those that do exist offer information through techniques that can be greatly improved.
G5.4.1-13	On-the-fly generated data representations when requested by users required.	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	To achieve an adequate COP, the different actors and disciplines must have at their disposal tools that update the information live and do so in a visually simple and understandable way.
G5.4.1-14	High risk exposure of first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Inadequate situational awareness often exposes first responders deployed to the scene of an incident or disaster to a higher than acceptable level of risk, sometimes resulting in serious injury or death.
G5.4.1-15	On scene volunteers rescuers command and COP	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Volunteers supporting emergency incidents cannot communicate and exchange information and data with the information system of the authorities. Thus, the incident command and the emergency operations centre, cannot have information about the status of the volunteers being involved in the incident.

Table 11 - Gaps from Common Operational Picture

Identification of gaps			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.2-1	Lack of a common approach in public early warning of disasters	LITERATURE	The vast majority of the society resides in areas that are prone to different types of natural hazards e.g., earthquakes, floods, tsunamis. There is not a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.

Identification of gaps			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.2-2	No standardized alerting procedure in National level	SURVEY	According to the answers from the questionnaire, there is no a standardized procedure at the National level for some countries of the alerting. Thus, can be easily identified a gap in the standardization across EU.
G5.4.2-3	Technical and procedural issues in alert and warning	LITERATURE	There is no homogeneity in relation to procedures, techniques and content related to warnings and early warning systems. Technical standards play an important role in communication systems. Common form to communicate disaster is important in all different countries, and even so more in cross border incident. Alert and warnings must be standardized for all stakeholders.
G5.4.2-4	No definition of "High priority public warnings"	LITERATURE	"High priority public warnings" refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. The identification of these messages is crucial to give those affected better options to preserve life and protect property, and this practice is not widespread.
G5.4.2-5	Different command competencies in alerts	SURVEY	There is no homogeneity in terms of the agencies responsible for warning and alerting the population (Civil Protection, fire brigade).
G5.4.2-6	Outdated warning systems	LITERATURE	In many cases, the technological resources to promote early warning and the appropriate issuing and dissemination of warnings are not up to date.
G5.4.2-7	Cross Border Alarms and Warnings gap	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Issued Alarms or Warnings in cross-border incidents are not available. This could create problems in their handling.
G5.4.2-8	Fight against misinformation and rumours or fake news	LITERATURE	Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Rumours and misinformation have been identified as a significant threat to the utility of social media and other online tools during disaster events.
G5.4.2-9	No follow-up of alarms and warnings issued	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	There is no mechanism available to monitor citizen's reactions after accepting Alarms or Warnings. As so, plans "assuming" their reaction might result to not desirable conditions

Table 12 -Gaps from Alert and warning

5.4.5. Gaps WP6

The WP6 (Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses) has the scope of plan, organise and implement international comparative research and analyses on the process of building a harmonisation framework for facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors

The above scope corresponds to sections and number of gaps identified in each one.

- 6.1 Resource federation and trusted information sharing. N° of gaps: 35
- 6.2 Education and training for first aid responses. N° of gaps: 23
- 6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness. N° of gaps: 8
- 6.4 Civil-Military cooperation. N° of gaps: 8
- 6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism. N° of gaps: 14

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D6.2.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-1	Non-technological initialisation of an emergency.	Professional experience	Communication between EU countries in cross-border incidents do not employ technological solutions for data exchange between countries. They typically communicate via phone.
G6.1-2	Cross-border data exchange in person.	Professional experience	Once the emergency is communicated, effectives from the affected countries move to the incident area and exchange information from the intervening agencies in person, without using technological solutions between countries.
G6.1-3	Lack of data federation between countries	Professional experience	EU countries do not implement data federation techniques to share information automatically and in real time with affected members of an emergency.
G6.1-4	Legal barriers between countries regarding resource federation	Literature	EU countries have different regulations in terms of data sharing between member countries and difficult the implantation of resource federation strategies.
G6.1-5	Dynamic management of data federation	Professional experience	There is a lack of dynamic data federation strategies in emergency scenarios.
G6.1-6	Use of pre-shared keys in symmetric cryptography	Professional experience	Symmetric cryptography uses pre-shared keys that, if stolen, could allow attackers to get access to the entire communication flow.
G6.1-7	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex infrastructure	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex hierarchy of certification authorities and trust relationships.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-8	Asymmetric cryptography is slow	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography operations are slower than those performed by symmetric cryptography.
G6.1-9	Data redundancy requires a considerable increase in disk space	Professional experience	The use of data redundancy techniques, such as RAID, substantially increase the disk space required to store the information.
G6.1-10	Data redundancy need to keep data up to date	Professional experience	Data coherence between data storage nodes increases the complexity to keep data up to date
G6.1-11	Inconsistencies in data redundancy	Professional experience	Distributed data in different nodes augments the likelihood of having inconsistent data.
G6.1-12	Emergency entities do not use dynamic network management techniques	Professional experience, Survey	Emergency environments use static networks for providing services, not considering dynamic network approaches such as SDN.
G6.1-13	On-demand security capabilities	Professional experience	Emergency organisations do not implement capabilities to offer security actuations on demand.
G6.1-14	Lack of standardised frameworks for data federation	Professional experience and literature	Although there are several frameworks available for data federation, none is widely used by emergency organisations at EU level.
G6.1-15	Existing frameworks are specific	Professional experience and literature	Current frameworks available are not general enough to be used in multidisciplinary emergency scenarios.
G6.1-16	Federation incompatibilities	Professional experience	The coexistence of multiple data federation techniques might present incompatibilities, such as OAuth 2.0 and its incompatibility with OAuth 1.0.
G6.1-17	OAuth2 - Complex management	Literature	The management of OAuth2 becomes complex when a substantial number of institutions intervene.
G6.1-18	OAuth2 - Centralised authorisation server	Professional experience	The authorisation server could be a single point of failure in case of attacks.
G6.1-19	Shibboleth - Lack of generalised logout capabilities	Literature	Shibboleth is not able to perform a logout action over all services federated at the same time.
G6.1-20	Shibboleth - High implementation complexity	Literature	The configuration of proxy servers is a complex task that difficult the implantation of a Shibboleth infrastructure.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-21	Quantum Menace	Literature	The threat that of the quantum computing against the current cryptosystems and the harvest-now-decrypt-later attacks.
G6.1-22	Computational cost	Literature	The computational cost required during cryptographic processes during emergency actuations might pose as an obstacle.
G6.1-23	Key distribution	Literature	An inappropriate or insecure key distribution can venerate the whole cryptosystem.
G6.1-24	Distributed technologies	Literature	Distributed integrity mechanisms, such as blockchain, might not be suitable for all the devices involved.
G6.1-25	PKI availability	Literature	The unavailability of PKI would disable the use of asymmetric schemes.
G6.1-26	Common data language	Professional experience	Define a common reference language for different entities and countries to support data integrity.
G6.1-27	Common data taxonomy	Professional experience	Define a common reference taxonomy for different entities and countries to classify data.
G6.1-28	Tampered data	Professional experience and literature	Use of blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing.
G6.1-29	Dynamic reference schema	Professional experience	Schema database to support different data integrity models.
G6.1-30	COP marking data source	Professional experience and Literature	COP marks the data displayed according to the data source (own or external).
G6.1-31	Backup data	Professional experience	Backup and restore data to mitigate data loss.
G6.1-32	Country specific requirements on exchange of personal / sensitive data	Professional experience, country specific GDPR law requirements	No possibility to legally exchange personal / sensitive data except via recognised international organisations. Access to personal / sensitive data should be arranged only via local GDPR law requirements.
G6.1-33	Lack of interoperability between frameworks offering data federation	Professional experience and literature	The different frameworks do not offer interoperability between them. This makes it difficult to share information between organisations.
G6.1-34	Trusted minimum requirements	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration on data sharing due to lack of trusted minimum requirements
G6.1-35	Unhelpful information	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration in data exchange due to unhelpful information provided by the frameworks

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	provided by the frameworks		

Table 13 – Gaps from Resource federation and trusted information sharing

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-1	European curricula for Basic First Aid	Literature	Cross-border co-operation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases to provide equivalent services between countries.
G6.2-2	Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses	Literature	It is not a universally valid European First Aid Certificate that guarantees a minimum knowledge base in first aid at within Europe.
G6.2-3	The specialty of emergency medicine	Literature	The specialty of emergency medicine is not recognised in all EU countries. It would be appropriate for the specialty to be recognised at European level in order to comply with the EU Doctors Directive and to ensure the free exchange of doctors between EU countries.
G6.2-4	Lack of homogeneity in the provision of health resources for emergency and urgent care.	Literature	In most European countries, emergency care teams consist of a doctor, nurse and ambulance driver. Doctors are not part of the non-emergency ambulance staff.
G6.2-5	Variable training of paramedics in European countries.	Literature	Cross-border cooperation in ICM requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and be able to provide equivalent services between countries.
G6.2-6	Lack of homogeneity in the response to multi-victim incidents.	Literature	In some countries there is no national standard operating procedure for dealing with multi-victim incidents.
G6.2-7	Ownership of emergency services.	Literature	The different ownership of emergency services (public, private...) hinders multi-agency training and education, as well as research and development. This hampers inter-sectoral cooperation.
G6.2-8	Lack of cooperation and mutual assistance between first aid providers	Literature	Each institution, organisation and team have the necessary skills and has the knowledge of the reaction but does not have the right communication and coordination system to achieve the best possible results.
G6.2-9	No standardised reporting after ICM and debriefing	Literature	There is no standardised reporting or debriefing after the management of an ICM, which would allow for a comparison of responses and lessons learned that could improve the response.

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-10	Lack of common methodology for the organisation of training exercises for first responders and no joint trainings for first responders	Literature / Professional experience	Currently there is not a common way for the organisation of first responders' training exercises. Many first responders' organisations have developed guidelines for the planning, conduct and evaluation of training exercises but no universal approach exists. Joint trainings for first responders (EMS, FRS, Police, etc.) would bring more efficiency into MCI management.
G6.2-11	Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions.	Literature	New technological innovations emerge, which can greatly facilitate first responders in their operations. On the other hand, if first responders are not sufficiently trained to these technologies beforehand, may result in reluctance and attachment in older and less effective solutions.
G6.2-12	No centralised "lessons learned database" for FAR at European level	Literature	The dissemination of lessons learned after drills and real emergencies within Europe is limited
G6.2-13	Knowledge, skills and competency spread between various groups of healthcare professionals who are tasked to participate in the management of MCI	Literature	The pathway to acquiring MCI and disaster management competencies is to obtain appropriate knowledge and skills that are reinforced through consistent drills and evaluations
G6.2-14	Didactical level of trainings	Literature	Many trainings or courses aim to deliver a didactical level of knowledge. Participants/professionals participate in educational initiatives without having any knowledge of disaster management principles, i.e., command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration
G6.2-15	Lack of rescuers with full medical education	Professional experience	Emergency medical care provided to victims by rescuers with very little medical education
G6.2-16	Lack of common organizational structure and rules regarding collaboration between first aid responders	Literature	More of the documents concerning protocols, standards and etc. are connected with a different level of administrative structures.
G6.2-17	Lack of uniform national standards for FARs	Literature	Most of the documents imply common information regarding the organization for first aid process.

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-18	Lack of capabilities for medical evacuating (MEDEVAC) by air	Literature	There are shortages regarding not having helicopters, system and pilots for medical evacuation by air. This prevents the execution of actions with a specialized helicopter. The military helicopters which are used in emergency situations are not suitable for these purposes.
G6.2-19	Insufficiency of modern field beds and other first aid gears inside the FARs vehicles	Literature	There are not enough first aid gears, including field beds, inside the FARs vehicles, because they were not thought to be used for mass casualty events. Some of the gear is also technically old and need replacement.
G.6.2-20	Lack of first aid courses by the BRC concerning the arriving time of the rescuing teams	Literature	There is a lack of courses for first aid provided by the BRC with the citizenry. Discounting the mandatory ones, which are taught to the candidates who are acquiring driving licence, there is a huge need for such courses to be taught in schools. Because not every citizen knows how to help someone in a disastrous situation before the arriving of the rescue team or medical doctor's help.
G.6.2-21	Lack of accessible locations of hospitals and other medical facilities in different regions of the country	Literature	There is significant displacement between the numbers of hospitals and other medical facilities in the country. There are even regions where no such facilities can be found. Excluding the bigger cities/administrative centres of the regions.
G.6.2-22	Lack of a common, national picture of vehicles/ambulances	Literature review and professional experience	In Greece, there is no available common information system that provides the available vehicle resources. Only 2 different systems are available in different regions.
G.6.2-23	Differences in the level of E&T (Medical doctors, nurses/equivalent, paramedics, etc.)	Literature review and professional experience	At the EU level there is no standardization of procedures and there are two main concepts: European and Anglo-American.
G.6.2-24	Lack of national standards and criteria for certification of FARs in Greece	Professional experience	There is a lack of certification in the training of medical first responders.

Table 14 - Gaps from Education and training for first aid responses

Identification of gaps			
Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.3-1	Lack of interoperability in communication tools	Professional experience	First responders communicate via various systems and channels. This leads to losing or interrupting information flow
G6.3-2	Hoaxes	Professional experience	Hoaxes are nowadays very popular and social media users often share/post unclear, changed or fake news
G6.3-3	Lack of understanding between agencies	Literature	The major misunderstanding is in terms of current roles and responsibility, including the understanding of each agency's capability and resource
G6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Literature	Destruction of infrastructure such a communication system is critical as well as the lack of coverage. During disaster such as MCI it is necessary to improve agency response, especially in terms of communication and reporting lines.
G6.3-5	Lack of public awareness	Literature	Low level of public awareness of the dangers, the possible consequences and readiness for adequate response in early warning and disaster disclosure. The development and implementation of Strategy for public awareness is needed.
G6.3-6	Communication language	Professional experience	Definition of the language in which the authority in charge must notify and inform the population when the MCI takes place in a cross-border region where two or more languages are spoken.
G6.3-7	Intentional misleading of first responders and civil protection service	Professional experience	Purposeful misleading and diverging of the servicemen – firefighters, rescue teams, civil protection and others.
G6.3-8	Lack of citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction	Professional experience	Citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction in a local-municipal level is not available

Table 15- Gaps from Raising practitioner and social awareness

Identification of gaps			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.4-1	Different scope of civil-military cooperation in EU countries.	Literature	In some countries, armed forces are only involved in major disasters and do not include the concept of civil-military cooperation in their security strategies.
G6.4-2	Lack of joint training, coaching and exercises	Literature	In some countries, the armed forces are not involved in disaster response planning and

Identification of gaps			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			preparedness. There is no sharing of training activities or exercises to facilitate the integration of the institutions.
G6.4-3	No official exchange of information between civil and military first responders based on "confidentiality"	Professional experience	"Confidentiality" restrictions based on different legal basis the civil and military units operate.
G6.4-4	Lack of protocols for coordination between military and civil actors	Literature	In some countries there are no accepted protocols for joint actions of military and civil teams in cases of disasters
G6.4-5	Lack of programs and standards for first responders Joint Education and Training	Literature	In most countries there are no adopted programs for joint training on uniform scenarios, common standards and procedures for joint actions of military and civilian teams in cases of natural disasters
G6.4-6	Lack of clarity on preparing for and conducting disaster and emergency operations and response planning	Literature	In most countries there are no clear and relevant to modern conditions procedures and action plans
G6.4-7	Lack of social awareness of the military's involvement and usefulness in the civilian sphere.	Literature	A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be in contributing to and assisting the civilian sphere. Not only in dealing with military conflicts of a more violent nature.
G6.4-8	Lack of political effort to include and develop the military as an instrument of assistance in emergency and civil protection situations	Literature	Normalizing the use of the military arm in politics to combat catastrophes, pandemics and natural disasters can be an important step towards the civilian sphere understanding its participation and normalizing processes.

Table 16 - Gaps from Civil-Military cooperation

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.5-1	Variability in the mode and degree of cooperation between authorities and civil protection.	Literature	The variability between the mode and degree of cooperation is due to different normative bases, forms of organisation and levels of competence.
G6.5-2	No common approach in the post-disaster social	Literature	Multi-casualty incidents may leave a mark both to the affected populations and first

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	and psychosocial support of victims as well as first responders.		responders, who operate on the field and face stressful situations. Many volunteering organisations provide psychological support to both groups. There is a need for a standardised approach or a widely adopted guideline to this direction.
G6.5-3	No clear UCPM cooperation	Literature	Need to better understand the scenarios in which the UCPM could be activated and what level of response should be expected from the mechanism, as well as the need to develop adequate host country support structures and procedures to receive assistance from UCPM.
G6.5-4	Lack of training on intercultural competences and foreign language skills in organisations active in civil protection	Literature	First responders are increasingly confronted with situations that require intercultural competencies and foreign language skills, requiring multicultural teams to act jointly or in a complementary manner in relation to these requirements in disaster situations
G6.5-5	Insufficient coordination and coherence between national and EU policies	Literature	While the European disaster management framework is advanced at regional level, significant legislative preparation remains to be done at national level.
G6.5-6	Integration of volunteers within the response SOP	Literature	Volunteers play a vital role throughout the emergency cycle so it is necessary to create an appropriate and recognised organisational and operational framework for volunteering.
G6.5-7	Joint exercises between volunteers and national authorities	Literature	Emergency preparedness capacity needs to be strengthened with qualified staff and volunteers. To this end, it is important that exercises at national and European level include the participation of these volunteers.
G6.5-8	Insufficient legislation for volunteers	Literature	Volunteer based organisations must be protected legally and integrated in government actions.
G6.5-9	Protection of volunteers	Literature	Organisations might need to ensure volunteers privately, i.e., by procuring an all-in insurance
G6.5-10	No centralised "lessons learned database" for Civil Protection at European level	Literature	The dissemination of lessons learned after field exercises and real situations within Europe is limited.
G6.5-11	Different approach to professional, volunteer	Professional experience	Extremely wide gaps in management, attitude to, ensuring of different types of

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	first responder teams and spontaneous volunteers		first responders on the field and in the training and preparation.
G6.5-12	Volunteers are not regulated by the law	Professional experience and literature	In some EU countries the status of Volunteer first responders is not legally regulated
G6.5-13	Volunteers and unified training at National level	Professional experience	In Greece, volunteer training is carried out by the organization in which each volunteer is a member.
G6.5-14	International disaster management coordinating organizations must develop a unified/aligned structure for their members' training, processes, and operational procedures	Professional experience and literature review	Harmonically operating forces and mechanisms from various nations are missing from international disaster management coordinating organisations. As a result, a unified/ aligned structure of their members' training, processes, and operational procedures is required.

Table 17 - Gaps from Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

5.5. Opportunities

5.5.1. Formant description

Based on the deliverables of the technological work packages and in the gaps identified in the previous point, related opportunities have been identified in different areas related to the project tasks.

5.5.2. Current status M12

Technology work packages (WP4, WP5 & WP6) based on prior identification of gaps have identified a number of opportunities.

A first version of the gaps has now been produced. These gaps are categorised in each of the work packages and their tasks and these mark their scope. In the coming months work will continue on these gaps in order to make a final delivery of these in the last stage of the project.

5.5.3. Opportunities WP4

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above.

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above. It is exactly the same scope and the same sections as these opportunities depend on the gaps.

Sections:

1. 4.1 First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units. N° of opportunities: 8
2. 4.2 Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals. N° of opportunities: 42
3. 4.3 Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies. N° of opportunities: 27
4. 4.4 The digitalization on first aid actuations. N° of opportunities: 16

5. 4.5 Instrumentation and health support wearables devices. N° of opportunities: 35

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D4.2.

Opportunities			
First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.1-1a	G4.1-1a	Accurate and live weather data	There are developed UAV systems using Quadrocopter technology with the necessary sensors to measure all possible weather data. They are robust enough to withstand freezing temperatures and high winds.
OP4.1-1b	G4.1-1b	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster areas	Aerial drones can be equipped with a variety of cameras from still photos to live video stream, both traditionally, low light and thermal images can be chosen. The drones come in a spectre of prices based on the quality of the technology from Go-pro technology with 1080 pixels up to 4k with 5000p. This gives an opportunity to make very detailed photos of the disaster area, with the possibility to zoom in on areas of interest.
OP4.1-2a	G4.1-2a	Tracking of personnel, equipment, and casualties	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically.
OP4.1-2b	G4.1-2b	Safe work environment for first responder personnel	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.
OP4.1-3a	G4.1-3a	Build ad hoc communication grids	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of datafiles and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.
OP4.1-3b	G4.1-3b	Distribution of equipment.	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, like bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding.

Opportunities			
First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.1-3c	G4.1-3c	Supply energy and charging capabilities	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother" vehicles can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
OP4.1-4	G4.1-4	Conduct search and relief missions	Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 18- Opportunities from First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.2-1	G4.2-2 G4.2-8 G4.2-34	Use of alternative communication systems	First responder agencies could use alternative communication systems in case of a system or network failure.
OP4.2-2	G4.2-1 G4.2-27	Extend network coverage	The different countries could improve the network coverage of the most used communication technologies to improve current coverage limitations.
OP4.2-3	G4.2-2	Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture	The VALKYRIES project identifies the adaptability of network technologies in the face of environmental adversities, with communications being fundamental to the transmission of critical data.
OP4.2-4	G4.2-3	Use of technologies that favour the extension of coverage to devices with fewer resources	The use of technologies that create wide coverage ranges favours the connection and, therefore, the transmissions of constrained devices.
OP4.2-5	G4.2-3	Use of mobile technologies to facilitate service delivery	Due to environmental adversities, the use of miniaturized cell phone technology, commonly known as decode-and-forward relays, can extend the coverage of mobile services to include hard-to-reach areas. This approach enables transmissions to large crowds, such as in relief camp settings, hard-to-reach urban areas, or rural locations where ground transportation has been disrupted.
OP4.2-6	G4.2-3	Use of UAVs for coverage extension in	Emergency areas may be in poor coverage or difficult to access locations, the use of devices

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		areas of difficult access or poor coverage	that can extend existing coverage is critical to the interoperability of VALKYRIES.
OP4.2-7	G4.2-3	Use of balloons to create communication routes in rural or poor coverage areas	Sometimes emergencies occur in remote locations or where a robust communications architecture does not exist, therefore, deploying devices that meet the needs of a fixed network architecture is necessary.
OP4.2-8	G4.2-4	Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted	The selection of technologies must be made depending on the type of data to be transmitted, being critical the relevant and indispensable information for the emergency.
OP4.2-9	G4.2-5	Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency	It is necessary to ensure that data transmissions over the communications networks are preferential to favour the exchange of data to devices operated by first responders and not by other entities (e.g., curious citizens, nearby personal vehicles, commercial radio stations, etc.).
OP4.2-10	G4.2-6	Unified regulations for data protection in emergency scenarios	There is an opportunity for a homogenised regulation regarding securitization of communications in emergency scenarios at EU level.
OP4.2-11	G4.2-7	Use of monitoring technologies or services capable of detecting threats that may affect the network	There is an opportunity for substantial improvement in network security by using active and passive monitoring systems capable of detecting threats to assets in real time.
OP4.2-12	G4.2-8	Improve intercommunication between technologies	There is room for standardisation work regarding interconnection of different technologies to allow changing easily between technologies.
OP4.2-13	G4.2-9	Use of technologies based on security constraints	EU regulations could focus on providing clear guidelines regarding which technologies or protocols are more suitable according to data security constraints in each scenario.
OP4.2-14	G4.2-10	Definition of backup guidelines at EU level	There is an opportunity for defining and implanting strict backup regulations enforcing emergency institutions to store sensitive data with redundancy to avoid information loss.
OP4.2-15	G4.2-11	Creation of data restoration contingency plans	The EU could design and implement recommendations or guidelines on how to proceed for data restoration in case of incidents.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-16	G4.2-12	Deployment of redundant services to provide back-up support in case of failure	The EU could provide recommendations for the deployment of auxiliary systems in multiple casualty scenarios.
OP4.2-17	G4.2-13 G4.2-16	Developing national ad hoc emergency networks	The creation of ad hoc national networks for emergency services (e.g., in Portugal, Ireland or Denmark) would help to ensure interoperability between the different emergency services.
OP4.2-18	G4.2-17	Leveraging 5G networks	The 5G network could provide an affordable, stable, and low-latency communications solution for autonomous and teleoperated vehicles and human intervention teams. In addition, functionalities such as Network Slicing could guarantee quality of service in crowded environments and ensure the confidentiality of a particularly critical network.
OP4.2-19	G4.2-24	Extend IOT data range	Long range local data gathering using Lora Network.
OP4.2-20	G4.2-25	Victims and FR data gathering	Wearable's sensors can collect victims and FR health data via Bluetooth and transmit them the network.
OP4.2-21	G4.2-26	Bridge between networks	To enable a wider network coverage, and overcome networks differences between entities, a gateway/bridge approach can be used to interconnect different networks and jointly cover a wider area.
OP4.2-22	G4.2-27	Increase RF area coverage	Use of drones with communications relay payload to increase the coverage of the FR communications.
OP4.2-23	G4.2-28 G4.2-29 G4.2-31	GATEWAY	To establish the connectivity bridge between different networks and translate from one network protocol to another network.
OP4.2-24	G4.2-32	IP LAYER	Establish IP layer as the reference network protocol for all the entities and communication that want to share data, within SIGRUN, to communication at IP level.
OP4.2-25	G4.2-30	Data Priority	Use gateways functions to implement the data priority established by the Command Centre, by using SLA and QoS, to ensure data transfer end-to-end based on the data prioritization.
OP4.2-26	G4.2-33	Data Conversion	APIs used by the SIGRUN, and the GATEWAYS provide the function to convert data formats, taxonomy, language, etc, between the

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			application to the SIGRUN refence established or other agreed by the entities.
OP4.2-27	G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Establish a redundant communications solution by integrating different networks and communication solutions into a common communications framework and architecture that enables bridging and multiple paths between different networks.
OP4.2-28	G4.2-34	GATEWAYS networks	By having gateways between different networks increases the redundancy by adding alternative so the communications.
OP4.2-29	G4.2-35	Data cluster	Data servers aggregated in clusters enables a higher redundancy, increase SLA and QoS performance and higher services availability.
OP4.2-30	G4.2-35	Data cluster	To improve the data redundancy, it should be data backup capability.
OP4.2-31	G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	An application agnostic federated system with the data status distributed enables a system function redundancy, in case of a function unavailable, other application can be deployed.
OP4.2-32	G4.2-37	Block Chain redundancy	Use the Blockchain networks to store shared metadata and transactional data.
OP4.2-33	G4.2-35	Data backup	Use of backup servers for the non-transaction and streaming data to add additional non-real time redundancy capability.
OP.4.2-34	G4.2-38	Shared Health data	Explore the potential use of EHR to exchange data between medial services.
OP4.2-35	G4.2-39	Querying data	Use of MQTT protocol to integrate data sources and data gathering within the SIGRUN sources.
OP4.2-36	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	Light cryptographic protocols	The use of light cryptographic protocols reduces the computing time and computing requirements.
OP4.2-37	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	RBAC/ABAC	The use or RBAC will atomize the data access which will allow to optimal control.
OP4.2-38	G4.2-20	Sectorization	Division or sectorization of incoming information.
OP4.2-39	G4.2-21	Access limitation	Limit network access and type of communication to a certain group of subscribers.
OP4.2-40	G4.2-22	Specific terminals for disasters	Either purchase or program existing terminals for unattended and simple use.
OP4.2-41	G4.2-19	Standard training in device use	Implementation of training standards and use of devices.

Opportunities			
Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-42	G4.2-23	Standard capabilities of emergency devices	Implementation of device technical requirements standards.

Table 19 - Opportunities from Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.3-1	G4.3-1 G4.3-2 G4.3-28	VR debriefing systems	Backing to Virtual Reality systems for FRs may be implemented to C2. Items likely training performance or training outputs might be improved the results. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-2	G4.3-3	Multiplatform. Run different OS	Interlinking applications. Note is a basic characteristic to standardise. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-3	G4.3-11 G4.3-24	Location of near/nearest vehicles	Not enough traceability of vehicles location from other organizations. Which technology could fulfil this opportunity? <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-4	G4.3-11	Georeferenced recording of events on the ground	Know-how disaster events. Monitor the location of the events and display by C2 application. Chance to track events in terms of geo-referencing. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-5	G4.3-7	COP standardization	Provide a global and real-time overview of the environmental situation and resources in the field.
OP-4.3-6	G4.3-11 G4.3-35 G4.3-36	HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces	Opportunity to have a constantly metrics of your vehicle, device or system. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
OP-4.3-7	G4.3-3 G4.3-45	Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios	Deploying emergency items in VUCA environments (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity). <i>Cross-border, Technological and Procedural</i>
OP-4.3-8	G4.3-2	Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness	AI capable of performing tasks commonly associated with human intelligence.
OP-4.3-9	G4.3-32	Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Predicting trends from previous exercises. Collecting and processing data to improve decision support.
OP-4.3-10	G4.3-32 G4.3-40	Social Network data visualization C2	Recap data from social network such as pictures, videos or current states in order to

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			increase decision-making and have a better understanding of the global situation. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-11	G4.3-28	Open Source C2 App	Providing technologies to the most vulnerable and under-resourced societies. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-12	G4.3-31	Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer	As weather prediction services use different standards and methodologies, this could be a critical gap in cross-border incidents effecting many parameters in decision making or logistics deployment. Recording such data, through available APIs, from ESA and/or NASA and/or ARATOS satellite systems, can resolve the gap through COP exchange between agents and countries by sharing the Hybrid Digital Twins recorded data.
OP-4.3-13	G4.3-7	Common Operational Picture exchange	As different agents within a country usually operate their own C2 systems, COP within a country using the VALKYRIES system and standards can be defined as all recording in the Hybrid Digital Twins of the VALKYRIES Core System. Then the COP exchange between countries (parametrized on permissions/restrictions as per bilateral agreements) can be easily performed.
OP-4.3-14	G4.3-32	Guidelines for social media crawling	EU members could elaborate recommendations for implementing social media crawling strategies.
OP-4.3-15	G4.3-32 G4.3-33 G4.3-40	Guidelines for selecting social media crawling tools	EU members could develop guidelines indicating the best tools and technologies used for social media data acquisition according to the type of platform consulted.
OP-4.3-16	G4.3-19	Drones' imagery data	Explore of multiple deployed drones in the field theatre to collect aerial view data (from EO/IR/ Lidar sensors) and increase the covered area, in particular for wide areas events.
OP-4.3-17	G4.3-18 G4.3-19 G4.3-22	Obtain high ground resolution data	Combine multiple data to improve the coverage and details of the in-field situation: 1) Drones imagery high resolution sensors and its flight level; 2) ground data sensors, from IOT deployable sensors of external IOT services; 3) In field imagery from FR and victims Smartphones.
OP-4.3-18	G4.3-21 G4.3-22	Airspace coordination with drones	New capability is required to manage the increasing number of flying elements in cases of Emergency / Disaster event, this can be

Opportunities			
Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			used by new solution or integration with external services.
OPx.3-19	G4.3-21 G4.3-38	RF space management	Add new capabilities to manage the RF spectrum as the number of communication infrastructures and radios is used with deployable sensors (Ground/ Air / Mobile /etc.).
OP-4.3-20	G4.3-34	Cross border data trace	Data shared between countries could be traced by establishing a countries agreement reference, as a sharing authorization schema, for which the data is validated prior to be shared, and enables trace of the that data.
OP-4.3-21	G4.3-35	Victims advance information	Only the data from victims assigned to a response medical facility is shared, from the moment it is assigned and including during transportation.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-36	Victims' historical data	The historical data collected during the event of a should be shared to the medical facility assigned to provide the medical service, including the information enabling its access to the victim EDR.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-41 G4.3-42	Traceability of victims and FR	Use of wearables and other portable sensors combined with communication capabilities to enable the C2 and medical services to locate and trace the FR and victims. Each data to the specific needs.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-39	External data	Specify API protocols and standard to enables external services to interface/share data with the SIGRUN
OP-4.3-23	G4.3-43	Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones	EU members could elaborate regulations and guidelines to harmonise the procedures of identifying dangerous zones.
OP-4.3-24	G4.3-44	Identification of relevant locations	EU members could define recommended technologies for the identification of relevant locations in emergency scenarios.
OP-4.3-25	G4.3-45	Use of decision-making applications	Implementation of decision support applications in emergency services.
OP-4.3-26	G4.3-46	Creation of operating procedures	Create operating procedures that collect the requirements of the standards used in equipment and devices.
OP-4.3-27	G4.3-46 G4.3-47	Incorporation of new standards	Create procedures to adapt equipment, devices, and infrastructures to the appearance of new standards.

Table 20 - Opportunities from Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies

Opportunities			
The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.4-1	G4.4-10	Digital Skills Improvement	To improve the digital skills of the first responder.
OP4.4-2	G4.4-2	Wearable's implementation	As it is expected to track information using smart instrumentation and wearables, it poses as a great opportunity to include their information in the digital environment.
OP4.4-3	G4.4-1 G4.4-2	European Iconographic Standardization	There is an opportunity to create an iconographic standard that accomplish with the desired requirements and avoid discrepancies.
OP4.4-4	G4.4-3 G4.4-4	European data standardization	To define a common standard for communications would ease the information sharing during emergencies and the connection with digitalization instances.
OP4.4-5	G4.4-5	Device's upgrade	To assure that the devices involved during first aid actuations accomplish with the required computational and graphical requirements, they should be evaluated and upgraded.
OP4.4-13	G4.4-13	Use of AI-based systems	It is possible to use AI-based systems for decision making or other considerations.
OP4.4-14	G4.4-11	Reduce voice communication	Digitization of first responders' actions will reduce reliance on voice communications.
OP4.4-15	G4.4-12	Reduce digital workload	Automating as many information flows as possible.
OP4.4-16	G4.4-8 G4.4-9	Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions	Taking first responders into consideration in the design of solutions for operational and C2 support in MCI and disasters is necessary to ensure that it provides them with the support they need with adequate usability, facilitating their tasks and not hindering them, and with reliability in real working conditions.

Table 21 - Opportunities from The digitalization on first aid actuations

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-1	G4.5-1	Use of wearables for tracking	It is possible to employ wearables that incorporate technologies such as RFID or NFC to track the stage of the incident each user is in.
OP4.5-2	G4.5-1	Use of wearables for tracking	Use of wearables incorporating GPS technology to track the location of each user in an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-3	G4.5-1	Use of wireless technologies in wearables	It is possible to use wearables that incorporate GPS technology for real-time

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			location of the users' position and thus associate them to a certain position/phase.
OP4.5-4	G4.5-2	Use of RFID-based wearables for identification	Through the use of RFID devices, it is possible to assign a unique identifier that allows users to be uniquely identified within an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-5	G4.5-2	NFC printing on traditional cards for identification	It is possible to print NFC tags on top of traditional cards to avoid a collapse due to lack of coverage.
OP4.5-6	G4.5-3	Prototyping with own technologies	It is possible to create a prototype of wearable devices that incorporates those modules to enable the necessary technologies to meet the needs raised.
OP4.5-7	G4.5-3	Firmware prototyping	It is possible to design firmware that incorporates a prototype to meet the needs that are required in such scenarios.
OP4.5-8	G4.5-4	Adaptive data delivery	To save battery power, data sending can be adapted depending on the patient's situation, sending data more continuously or in a reduced form.
OP4.5-9	G4.5-5	RFID to avoid batteries	RFID-based devices avoid the use of batteries in these devices and therefore the limitation of the lifetime.
OP4.5-10	G4.5-11 G4.5-13	Communicate by voice	It would be possible to implement the functionality of wearables that do not have them with a microphone and a speaker to allow local communication between FRs.
OP4.5-11	G4.5-17	Communication by text	Wearables that have screens could transmit and receive text messages to and from C2.
OP4.5-12	G4.5-11	Warning of a danger for FRs	There are integrations in some wearables that allow you to report a personal physical threat via an easy action (panic button) o detection of lying position and lack of movement. This information is correlated by the GPS coordinates of the RF and also the opening of an ambient microphone. The use of these solutions should be more widespread. In addition to this it could be interesting to be able to report via the wearable the localization of different dangers (fire, smoke, collapse) that identify NO-GO zones to report them to FRs approaching that zone.
OP4.5-13	G4.5-1 G4.5-25 G4.5-26	Automatic transmission of vital signs of FRs	It would be possible to transmit to C2 automatically (continuously, at defined intervals, on request) vital signals of the FRs detected by the wearables. For example,

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			heart rate, oxygen saturation, but also lack of movement could be detected.
OP4.5-14	G4.5-14	Integration of sensors for hazardous substances	The possibility of integrating sensors for various hazardous substances within wearables (e.g., helmets) would allow continuous monitoring of dangers. The possibility of transmitting this information, correlated for example by the GPS coordinates, to C2 would make it immediately available to all FRs in the area, triggering an alarm when they approach danger.
OP4.5-15	G4.5-13	Broadcasting of safety and security information	Ability to transmit information on the safety and security of FRs through wearables. Preceded by a pre-established warning signal, they can be short text or audio messages or, in the case of devices with larger screens, contain images relating to the location of the danger.
OP4.5-16	G4.5-15	Create common procedures for disaster fatality identification between different countries	Sharing certain information about deceased victims obtained through wearables can provide a common basis for the harmonization of DVI procedures among different countries. The more accurate and verified the identification, the easier it will be to agree on a shared regulation. This solution may be difficult to implement due to political problems.
OP4.5-17	G4.5-14	Freezing the scene of a deceased victim discovery	The ability to capture via a wearable device (body cam, smart glasses) images and the exact location of a scene before recovering a deceased victim would provide authorities responsible for identifying the victim with valuable information. This data could be securely transmitted and stored.
OP4.5-18	G4.5-18	Acquire unique IDs of implanted wearables	The ability to “read” an implantable wearable and correlate its ID with a person’s medical record would allow a person to be identified with certainty and quickly.
OP4.5-19	G4.5-14	Record victim’s data in blockchain	The ability to log data in blockchain will be provided by the VALKYRIES’ system for all crucial transactions and metadata. This can also cover the recording of all medical data gathered in different stages of triage or

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			handling of the victim between different agents, up to the entry of the victim to the final hospital to take care.
OP4.5-20	G4.5-10 G4.5-20	Use of first responder's telecom devices to record victim's data as per its wearable unique id	In case we use the combination of NFT wearables and blockchain, then the communication to the appropriate C2 or supporting federated software can be performed using the communication capabilities of the smart phone/tablet of the first responder initiating/updating or retrieving information on a trusted "need to know" basis.
OP4.5-21	G4.5-25 G4.5-26	Collect victim's vital signs	Use of smart wearables, devices, and smartphones to collect in near real-time victim's vital signs, possibly including, but not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Heart rate ○ Body Temperature ○ Oxygen levels and saturation ○ Abrupt movements ○ Blood pressure
OP4.5-22	G4.5-26	Monitor patient vital signs	The vital signs collected can be transmitted to the medical centre that records the vital signals history and generated a victim's dashboard, monitoring the key values of the patient signals and raise alerts.
OP4.5-23	G4.5-22	Mask victims ID from victim's signs	For purpose of privacy protection, the identification data of the victims and the victims' vital signs could be masked with alias. Only the identification service would be able to cross this information by authorization of the victims.
OP4.5-24	G4.5-20	Patient vital signs available to medical service	The victim current and historic vital signs data are shared with the assigned medical service for treatment.
OP4.5-25	G4.5-17 G4.5-22	Victim's vital signs on route	While on route, the ambulances carrying the victims are equipped with the means to, either directly collect the victim's vital signs or to recover that data from the victim's sensors artifacts (wearables, smart devices, etc), and send them to the medical service of destination.
OP4.5-26	G4.5-18	Victim ID	Use of pre-tagged RF, WR code, and marked colour to mark a victim. Registration of the victim with personal data can be done by FR. Victim's signals are mask with the TAG, not with the victim's name or ID.

Opportunities			
Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-27	G4.5-23	Telemedicine service	A telemedicine service can be set-up to provide assistance to responders aiding a victim.
OP4.5-28	G4.5-23	Telemedicine guidance	Telemedicine can provide audio assistance to responders to 1) guide them in applying lifesaving procedures and, 2) help performing assessment of the victim's health condition and basic diagnostics.
OP4.5-29	G4.5-23	Telemedicine data collection	The telemedicine service can receive imagery from the victims and use of remote experts to confirm/help achieve a diagnostic.
OP4.5-30	G4.5-22	European Health Data Space	EU Proposal to expand the use of electronic health data to deliver health care to the individual from whom those data were collected ("primary use") and to improve research, innovation, policy making, patient safety, personalised medicine, official statistics or regulatory activities ("secondary use").
OP4.5-31	G4.5-25	Use of wearables on critically ill patients	The use of wearables in critically ill patients should be analysed in more detail.
OP4.5-32	G4.5-26 G4.5-27	Establish an international standard for wearable functionalities	To ensure the reliability of the measurements provided by wearables. All wearable manufacturers should manufacture according to an international standard.
OP4.5-33	G4.5-27 G4.5-29	Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations	Implementing medical regulations in wearables, these devices would be more useful for first responders.
OP4.5-34	G4.5-18 G4.5-25 G4.5-28	Providing first responders with wearables	It would allow the physical and mental condition of first responders to be monitored and taking decisions
OP4.5-35	G4.5-7 G4.5-18 G4.5-25	Implementing the use of wearables among first responders	Ensure that the physical and mental conditions of first responders are correct.

Table 22 - Opportunities from Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

5.5.4. Opportunities WP5

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above.

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above. It is exactly the same scope and the same sections as these opportunities depend on the gaps.

In the same way as in the gaps in this WP5, tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.4 have been divided in order to correctly categorise the identified opportunities.

Sections:

1. 5.1.1 Crisis response planning. N° of opportunities: 7
2. 5.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage. N° of opportunities: 14

3. 5.2.1 Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment. N° of opportunities: 7
4. 5.2.2 Others maintenance, logistics and deployment. N° of opportunities: 5
5. 5.3 Command and control and support to operational decision-making. N° of opportunities: 16
6. 5.4.1 Common Operational Picture. N° of opportunities: 11
7. 5.4.2 Alert and warning. N° of opportunities: 8

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D5.2.

Opportunities		
Crisis response planning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.1-1	Regulatory harmonisation	In order to promote the establishment of unified cross-border response plans and procedures, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to harmonise them.
OP5.1.1-2	Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation	In multi casualty incidents, in which the coordination and collaboration of different first responders agencies are required, it is crucial that data and information exchanged through the various systems should be interpreted in the same way by first responders. Apart from semantics that are used in systems, it is essential for FRs among the EU Member States to adopt a common terminology and symbology. This could lead to better collaborations and to the accomplishment of a common operational picture and situational awareness. Moreover, common signals and symbols could be used in social media for early warning.
OP5.1.1-3	Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.	Developing, updating, revising and publishing crisis management plans on regular basis. This should be stated in the specific law.
OP5.1.1-4	Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.	Good emergency planning is not effective if it is not accompanied by an adequate dissemination plan that includes the potentially affected population and training for all those involved in the response.
OP5.1.1-5	Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system	A federated system could facilitate harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines.
OP5.1.1-6	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures and the supported role definitions "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management. Common role definitions and

Opportunities		
Crisis response planning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		workflows will be included only for the support of the Core of SIGRUN system.
OP5.1.1-7	C2 activation through a common federated system / COP	Signalling of the need to activate C2 through the COP exchange/sharing of the Valkyries / SIGRUN system

Table 23- Opportunities from Crisis response planning

Opportunities		
Reconnaissance and triage		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-1	Harmonisation of emergency services structure	Greater homogeneity in the structure and composition of the emergency services would favour greater homogeneity in the organisation of the chain of command and operational procedures. Given that this goal is almost impossible, harmonisation between the commanders of the emergency services working together would be the priority.
OP5.1.2-2	Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation of training and competencies for emergency services professionals at EU level.
OP5.1.2-3	Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.	Legislation to encourage the development and integration of joint EMS-hospital MCI response plans, with EMS and hospitals taking a more proactive role to maximise the effectiveness of the response.
OP5.1.2-4	Standardisation of terminology and criteria.	Standardisation of terminology and harmonisation of criteria for zoning in MCI response would make it easier for different agencies or regions to work together.
OP5.1.2-5	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be collected in relation to each victim is fundamental to guarantee traceability and continuity of care for those affected in a disaster, even more so in cross-border disasters. Of great interest is the use of reliable mobile applications that, while guiding the first responder in their work, allow for easy recording and sharing of relevant victim information.
OP5.1.2-6	Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI.	Use "clever" coloured wristbands (equipped with electronic readable id) in first triage/victim identification, log the data in secured blockchain structure and allow other rescuers handling the victim

Opportunities		
Reconnaissance and triage		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		to record more data, prior to the handling of the victim in a hospital.
OP5.1.2-7	Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI.	Standardisation in the triage, coding and tagging of disaster victims is essential to ensure traceability and continuity of care for those affected, especially in disasters where different agencies or countries have to work together. In the simplest or most difficult conditions, standardising the triage priority codes, the tagging and the victim information recording (e.g., via a standardised triage tag, via a mobile application or via a wearable) has proven to be a simple way to support the interoperability of first responders.
OP5.1.2-8	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional and scientific societies competent in emergency medicine in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations on triage, on-scene care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thereby promoting quality standards in line with current scientific evidence.
OP5.1.2-9	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management.
OP5.1.2-10	Improving real-time victims' clinical information	Accessing to different parameters could help in choosing the patient's destination
OP5.1.2-11	Improving vehicles tracking	Acquire the arrival and set which is the entry point, the person who detects it, transmitting information to SIGRUN to facilitate its management and use
OP5.1.2-12	Improving the first responders training	Approach studies of first responders by integrating lessons learned from past disasters.
OP5.1.2-13	Standardization of first responders training and certification in Europe	First responders (EMS, FRS) should have standardised common training and knowledge in order to have a quality level of rescue.

Opportunities		
Reconnaissance and triage		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-14	Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters	Debriefings after each incident, drill, operation are essential. Debriefings shall be well structured and should describe each operation which was made during intervention, because many issues raise only after the operation. Step-by-step approach and clear identification of the roles of first responders. IRS and First responders (EMS, FRS, Police...) should use a common debriefing and evaluation after the intervention. Common trainings for First responders - practice cooperation and make procedures more efficient. It is necessary to set processes, responsibilities of each First responder and uniform evaluation.

Table 24 - Opportunities from Reconnaissance and triage

Opportunities		
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.1-1	Improving communications	Real-time sharing of acquired information necessary
OP5.2.1-2	Technological updating of emergency services	Updating the ICT resources used by the emergency services would greatly simplify current operational procedures, make them more efficient, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.
O9P5.2.1-3	Technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by emergency services transferring information by digital data or another communication system would simplify communication procedures, make them more efficient by fostering the development of a common situational awareness, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.
OP5.2.1-4	ICT technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT assets used by the emergency services would reduce the use of alternative communications resources outside common channels, thus promoting the development of appropriate common situational awareness.
OP5.2.1-5	Improving portability	Interoperability could be achieved if systems could interface using formatted messages, e-mail, or import/export functions

Opportunities		
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.1-6	Technological e-health updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by the emergency services would increase the diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities of the first medical responders on the scene.
OP5.2.1-7	Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.	Digitalisation solutions for EMS intervention in MCI and disasters must also address as an important objective the recording of automatic or sensor-based data and in general the simplification of the work of first responders in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual.

Table 25 - Opportunities from Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment

Opportunities		
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.2-1	Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.	In addition to the development of cross-border collaborative plans, EU countries should seek the development of unified procedures among the services involved regarding the planning and logistical response to an MCI or disaster affecting several countries.
OP5.2.2-2	Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.	Standardisation in deployment support elements, such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to establish an advanced medical post, would favour logistical interoperability between agencies and territories in MCI or disaster response.
OP5.2.2-3	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional societies competent in emergency response in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations regarding the planning and logistical response of emergency services to an MCI or disaster.
OP5.2.2-4	Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.	Progress needs to be made in the use of technological tools and national information systems to ensure that logistical preparedness and response to national and cross-border incidents is effective.
OP5.2.2-5	Strengthen logistics expertise	It is advisable to develop specialised formal education, homogenised across EU countries, to provide logistics training for emergency services professionals involved in these aspects of disaster response.

Table 26 - Opportunities from Others maintenance, logistics and deployment

Opportunities		
Command and control and support to operational decision-making		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-1	Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation in the distribution of competencies between emergency services within the EU. In the meantime, it is necessary to favour the highest degree of harmonisation to facilitate interoperability between disaster management mechanisms in different countries.
OP5.3-2	C2 self-adaptive network environment	Resilient and self-adaptive network environment due to high complexity response of the task.
OP5.3-3	Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.	In order to ensure unity of action in the C2 of the emergency, it is necessary that all services involved in the response can be integrated into a single emergency operations centre.
OP5.3-4	Municipality supportive agents' engagement	Use the same track and trace technologies and devices to municipalities' assets in order to track their availability and status in COP
OP5.3-5	Define criteria for C2 facilities location	Establish criteria for the location of CEOC, Incident Command Post ICP and the Advanced Medical Post AMP, based on the communications coverage and scope of the incident.
OP5.3-6	Harmonization of procedures	Harmonisation of operational competencies and procedures, determination of the minimum dataset and establishment of basic interoperability standards.
OP5.3-7	Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.	Definition of an EU harmonised Control and Command System (C2S) framework adapted to the breadth of the territory and the severity of the new challenges.
OP5.3-8	Simplify information flow	Simplify the information exchange process. Fewer steps, fewer errors.
OP5.3-9	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU could facilitate the definition of joint workflows between C2 systems and the design of specific training programmes.

Opportunities		
Command and control and support to operational decision-making		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-10	Technological updating of emergency services	Identify systems that do not allow for the integration of needs for emergency services. Propose an action plan for the purchase of new equipment.
OP5.3-11	Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system	To be able to share information between systems in a supranational environment.
OP5.3-12	Improving communications	Communications improvements in terms of data sharing. Real-time is a must for MCI.
OP5.3-13	Blockchain "logbooks"	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks"
OP5.3-14	Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks" synchronizing the clocks of the federated systems with a central one provided by SIGRUN
OP5.3-15	Facilitating research through a common federated system	The recording of data, in addition to assisting in the real-time management of the emergency, provides a posteriori data that describe in detail the sequence of events in a real incident, allowing an objective analysis and thus the evaluation of procedures, the identification of areas for improvement, greater knowledge of the behaviour of these disasters, etc.
OP5.3-16	Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool	Map all digitized data into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria

Table 27 - Opportunities from Command and control and support to operational decision-making

Opportunities		
Common Operational Picture		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-1	Regulatory harmonisation	To encourage interoperability between cross-border C2. Information exchange technologies and platforms, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to encourage harmonisation.

Opportunities		
Common Operational Picture		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-2	Fostering a culture of information exchange	It is necessary to work on the individual, organisational and political culture to foster an attitude committed to the need to share all relevant information that allows for maintaining adequate situational awareness in disaster response. A culture of information sharing between institutions would facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning, and adaptation and improvisation.
OP5.4.1-3	Taking volunteers into account	COP of the available data from the volunteers in a common system for the effective utilization of the volunteer human resources.
OP5.4.1-4	Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be exchanged between disaster managers is essential for the interoperability of emergency services and decision support systems. There is a need to improve C2 communication at inter-agency, cross-sectoral and cross-border levels. Harmonisation of standards at EU level would be desirable to create a unified basis that can be applied in each country. Deciding what information is relevant is a critical task for developers of information exchange systems between institutions.
OP5.4.1-5	C2 applications	Integrate information from other agencies into command-and-control applications for each cross-border emergency service
OP5.4.1-6	Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments	VR goggles and see a visual fly out of entire joint schemes of manoeuvre, war-gaming COAs real time while discussing them with the distributed planning staff who used the same environment to build the plans
OP5.4.1-7	Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters	Study and learn from every advanced visualisation technique used in other sectors of society and try to apply their usefulness to an emergency situation.
OP5.4.1-8	On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques (dendrograms, stream graphs, hive plots...)	In order for the image and information to be updated live, it is necessary that a person intervening in the emergency has the function of interacting with the system that provides the COP and constantly updates it with the data it receives. Some elements could be updated with the use of well positioned sensors, cameras and so on.

Opportunities		
Common Operational Picture		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-9	Facilitating a COP through a common federated system	Use available satellite services monitoring weather and their results (such as Copernicus or Aratos Satellite), map the weather conditions as layers in COP/Hybrid Digital Twins and exchange through a common federated system / COP
OP5.4.1-10	Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters	Creating a COP that provides realistic, situationally aware information, tailored so that its visualisation can be understood by agencies of different types, is essential. But it will also be necessary for the user to have options within the COP to access more specific information in their field.
OP5.4.1-11	Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.	It is difficult to fully ensure the safety of first responders during a disaster, but in addition to providing adequate means and fostering an adequate safety culture in the emergency services, it is essential to maintain adequate situational awareness at all times.

Table 28 - Opportunities from Common Operational Picture

Opportunities		
Alert and warning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-1	Defining a common approach to disaster early warning	There is an opportunity for a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.
OP5.4.2-2	Identifying "high priority public warnings"	Documents and guides have been published in order to describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property.
OP5.4.2-3	Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe	The alert of MCI incidents should be comprehended and common at European level and subsequently at national and local level. The notification must be common, as, in the case of an MCI incident that occurs at a cross-border point, the alert and notification responsibilities and procedures must be standardized for all stakeholders.

Opportunities		
Alert and warning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-4	Standardization of alerts information and systems in Europe	A single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth). Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by U.S IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities. The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings. Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.
OP5.4.2-5	Technological upgrading of warning systems	Adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts.
OP5.4.2-6	Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool	Map all digitized data, including alarms and warnings issued, into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria
OP5.4.2-7	Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters	Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news.
OP5.4.2-8	Social media analysis of citizens behaviour	Social media and apps analysis of citizens behaviour. Out of the scope of the Valkyries project.

Table 29 - Opportunities from Alert and warning

5.5.5. Opportunities WP6

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above.

The opportunities shown in the work package are related to the gaps above. It is exactly the same scope and the same sections as these opportunities depend on the gaps.

Sections:

- 6.1 Resource federation and trusted information sharing. N° of opportunities: 28
- 6.2 Education and training for first aid responses. N° of opportunities: 13
- 6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness. N° of opportunities: 6
- 6.4 Civil-Military cooperation. N° of opportunities: 6
- 6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism. N° of opportunities: 6

This is a report further information can be found in the specific deliverable D6.2.

Opportunities		
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-1	Use of resource federation techniques	The Valkyries project identifies an opportunity for implementing data federation and data sharing strategies between EU members in emergency situations.
OP6.1-2	Create a common regulation for resource federation at the EU level	Creating a new EU-level federation regulation could allow countries to effectively share sensitive data between affected members following GDPR guidelines.
OP6.1-3	Dynamic management of data federation	The EU could define guidelines indicating the best principles to implement dynamic data federation strategies, as well as creating regulations for their implantation for all EU members.
OP6.1-4	Use of temporal session keys	Since using pre-shared keys for protecting communications is not recommended, we encourage as an opportunity for improvement the use of temporal keys derived from an initial key, reducing the impact of attacks on confidentiality.
OP6.1-5	Generate a certification authority at EU level for emergencies	The creation of a certification authority at EU level for its use in emergency situations could considerably simplify the complexity of the public key infrastructure required in these scenarios.
OP6.1-6	Use of hybrid cryptographic solutions	In practise, applications commonly use a hybrid approach between symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. The first one is used for encrypting the data transmitted, while the latter is employed for key distribution. There is an opportunity for standardisation in this regard at EU level, particularly in medical scenarios, and for the use of Decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials.
OP6.1-7	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data storage	There is an opportunity for improving the efficiency of protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, optimising storage resources.
OP6.1-8	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data coherence	There is an opportunity for improving current protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, taking into consideration data coherence between nodes.
OP6.1-9	EU regulations regarding data redundancy	The EU could put efforts in creating guidelines or regulations offering recommendations about the most suitable technologies to avoid these situations.
OP6.1-10	Dynamic network management	Emergency services could benefit from using dynamic network management principles such as SDN to reconfigure

Opportunities		
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		the network to offer more adaptability and better services, reducing the cost.
OP6.1-11	On-demand security capabilities	There is room for regulations indicating how to manage emergency networks in a dynamic way to offer security capabilities on demand.
OP6.1-12	EU Regulations regarding data federation framework	It would be desirable that all EU members adopt a common framework offering data federation. Therefore, it is necessary to establish regulations, with respect to data federation and frameworks.
OP6.1-13	Definition of general data federation frameworks	There is an opportunity for designing and creating a general enough framework to include all particularities of the different emergency services operating in the EU.
OP6.1-14	Federation incompatibilities	EU regulations could offer a list of federation technologies that should be implemented by all federation platforms and technologies to comply with the EU regulation.
OP6.1-15	OAuth 2.0 - Optimised designs for data federations	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems keeping a low structural complexity.
OP6.1-16	OAuth 2.0 - Redundant authorisation server	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems based on OAuth using load balancing techniques over multiple authorisation servers.
OP6.1-17	Shibboleth - Single Sign Out	Valkyries identifies an opportunity to improve the Shibboleth standard by incorporating single sign out capabilities.
OP6.1-18	Shibboleth - Reduce implementation complexity	There is an opportunity for improving the Shibboleth standard to ease the complexity of proxy servers.
OP6.1-19	PQC KEM hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient cypher cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.
OP6.1-20	PQC DSA hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient signature cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.
OP6.1-21	Quantum Key Distribution	The implementation of QKD systems would provide information-theoretically secure keys to the cryptosystem.
OP6.1-22	Light cryptographic methods	The use of lighter algorithms will ease the implementation using less powerful devices.
OP6.1-23	Distributed PKI	The use of distributed PKI would avoid the problems of availability related to network failures during emergency actuations.
OP6.1-24	Common data language, taxonomy and reference schema	Use of a scheme Library supported on a database, where the library holds different cooperation reference schemas allows each event to negotiate establish and store the schema used by the event, or reuse in future events. It enables a federated system to define a common reference frame for data sharing

Opportunities		
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-25	Tampered data	Use of Blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing
OP6.1-26	COP marking data source	Establish a COP definition to mark differently external and own data sources displayed
OP6.1-27	Backup data	Define a backup service to collect all the data: Block-chain for transactional data, and for all the exchanged metadata. Local data backup capability to provide resilience and adaptability in case of connectivity lost. Establish an automatic restore capability in case of temporary data lost
OP6.1-28	High level framework	Without changes in the current framework. Define a high-level framework that translates de data and make this interoperable- (SIGRUN).

Table 30 - Opportunities from Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

Opportunities		
Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.2-1	Common core curriculum for the speciality of emergency medicine	The WHO provides a classification and minimum standards for emergency medical teams that could serve as a basis for a European classification.
OP6.2-2	European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur)	This curriculum could increase the number of countries offering this type of training at the undergraduate level, which would raise the level of competence of paramedical professionals in general.
OP6.2-3	Cooperation and coordination between institutions	Facilitate the exchange of information necessary for decision-making by the different services involved in the emergency response.
OP6.2-4	Standardisation of reports and debriefing	Implementation of a system based on the EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network and Lessons Learned Programme or WHO Guidance for After Action Review. Standardised data collection could facilitate the compilation of the information in a global database.
OP6.2-5	Creation of a lessons learned database for FARs at European level	A global database of lessons learned would connect outcomes that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.2-6	Creation of a universally valid European First Aid Certificates	These certificates should be issued by a National accredited institution after a specific training recognised via EQF and be conducted by the EU-OSHA, based on the guidelines of the ERC.
OP6.2-7	Creation of a Register of European First Aid members.	A European First Aid Certificate opens the opportunity to create a European register of qualified personnel for the intervention in Mass Casualty Incident (MCI).

Opportunities		
Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		These types of registries help the development of international and cross-border protocols.
OP6.2-8	Conduct of simulation exercises	Development of educational software for simulations of disasters, accidents and catastrophes for educational purposes. The software, in this sense, will contribute to the quality and effect of the overall training process in the direction of forming and upgrading the practical skills of employees for risk assessment, timely management decision-making, ensuring appropriate coordination, and emergency control and response systems situations. The purpose of its development is for every employee of the FARs to be registered in the specified platform and to have access to training materials for various courses and trained
OP6.2-9	Creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes.	This initiative is imperative from the point of view of refining the conceptual apparatus, because the declaration of a state of emergency requires the existence of a law defining extraordinary events.
OP6.2-10	Transformation of General Directorate of Fire Safety and Protection of the Population	Transformation of the structure on the basis of the relief and climatic features of the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria. This will lead to optimization not only of the capabilities that these structures will have, but also lead to an appropriate use of resources
OP6.2-11	Acquisition of new vehicles and equipment from neighbouring countries, NATO and EU partners	A consistent and efficient policy for acquisition is required on the government level. On regional and international levels, cooperation between the neighbours which are part of same organizations is considered to be a good practice. Therefore, a trade of new vehicles and equipment between them is also in consideration. The old ones can be sold, used for last time by the partners in hazardous regions or be sliced into pieces.
OP6.2-12	Creation of first aid and paramedic help for school and university programs	Enhancement of the presence in the citizens' life from the earliest moments with a volunteer program curriculum. This way the level of saved lives until first aid arrives will increase. By making this program voluntary will test the efficiency of the program. If extremely needed and after a test period the program can become obligatory curriculum.
OP6.2-13	Establishment and rebuilding of some of	The whole process is a prolonging one which requires finance from the government as well as additional funding

Opportunities		
Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
	the former first aid institutions	from the EU cohesive fund. Also, the political site of the issue must be addressed here, with the passing of amendments to the existing law for health care. If needed an additional supporting law must be accepted by the Parliament.

Table 31 - Opportunities from Education and training for first aid responses

Opportunities		
Raising practitioner and social awareness		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.3-1	SIGRUN application	Providing advanced communications, information sharing and tactical C&C services for the first (first-aid) responders
OP6.3-2	VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) have been established in many countries to help authorities manage information in high-pressure information environments. These teams monitor social media, support situational awareness, counter rumours and disseminate official communication. Establishing this kind of teams within all EU countries.
OP6.3-3	Debriefing sessions after each incident or disaster	This is an issue that also arise in D5.2. Debriefing sessions after the intervention are missing or unappreciated parts of the incident or disaster
OP6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Provide the back-up plan in the case of failure of ordinary used systems
OP6.3-5	Strategy for public awareness	Development of Strategy for public awareness
OP6.3-6	Unified communication language	Design of a catalogue of visual warning signs (indicative signs, colour codes) or auditory signs (alarms) to alert and inform the population.

Table 32 - Opportunities from Raising practitioner and social awareness

Opportunities		
Civil-Military cooperation		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.4-1	Implementation of European civil-military doctrine.	At the European level, the Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance has been developed to provide basic guidelines and standards for planning and executing operations in support of civilian structures. There is also a training centre
OP6.4-2	Shared understanding brought about by working together, connecting, education	Through creation and adoption of unified guidance, procedures and TTPs for applying the capabilities of CIMIC specialists and experts in disaster settings will provide greater clarity on the contribution and future actions of civil and military actors in such operations.
OP6.4-3	Development of national requirements and	By developing national requirements and a program to build capabilities to implement joint civil-military

Opportunities		
Civil-Military cooperation		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
	capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures for disasters, accidents and catastrophes	procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes, better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams will be achieved
OP6.4-4	Programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams developing	If programs and scenarios are developed for the joint training of civil-military teams, then in cases of natural disasters, they will immediately begin the implementation of the developed and mastered practical procedures for providing assistance to the population
OP6.4-5	Amendment of the current Law for defense of classified information	The current application and use of the law is not perfect, it needs amends, which would help speed up the process by which the medical staff will gain access to classified information. Such amendments can be in the period in which the access is granted and the waiting is shortened for example by two-three weeks.
OP6.4.-6	Insertion of new technology and checkpoints for communication with neighboring country	Enhancing the level of communication between neighboring countries is an important matter in potential and enduring cooperation between the neighbors on civil and on military level.

Table 33 - Opportunities from Civil-Military cooperation

Opportunities		
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.5-1	Encourage the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills in the training for first responders to cross-border MCI	To ensure compatibility and complementarity between intervention teams, the UCPM provides a training programme. The training helps experts improve their coordination and assessment skills in disaster response, but it should be complemented with the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills.
OP6.5-2	Integration of volunteers into the emergency operational procedures	Define the roles, "chain of command", liability and the way to operate within the emergency cycle for volunteers.
OP6.5-3	Guarantee the involvement of volunteers in field exercises	Field exercises test the specific response capabilities, self-sufficiency, interoperability, coordination and procedures of the different actors and their response material. The UCPM should ensure that volunteers participate in its field exercises, as they are one of the actors involved.
OP6.5-4	Ensure protection of volunteers during their operation exploring insurance field.	Follow a strategic approach by defining a limited area of assistance as well as risk-free activities for those volunteers who are not protected by insurance.

Opportunities		
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.5-5	Creation of a lessons learned database in Civil Protection	A global database of lessons learned would make easier to connect outcomes from past that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.5-6	Introduction of first aid spontaneous volunteers management course/ programme	In the large-scale disasters usually a large number of medical and non-medical staff volunteers to support field operations. So far there is no unified training programme how to manage those people.

Table 34 - Opportunities from Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

5.6. Standardization roadmap

Figure 2 - European pre-standardization map and joint roadmap

5.7. Roadmap justification

VALKYRIES is on track with the roadmap.

VALKYRIES project has a strong complexity as it is being developed by companies and researchers from different countries, with different expertise and professional skills, which may affect the project development and timeline.

Nevertheless, the project is succeeding to follow the roadmap.

6. Next steps

The next steps will be to continue the harmonisation process within the work packages that support the technological ones. But the most important will be the results of the technological work packages in the coming months.

Harmonisation opportunities will be analysed and studied in the coming months and some of them will become outputs of the project.

7. Annex A – Legal standard Identification

7.1. UC1 – Spain - Portugal

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	(Madrid) Order 1102.2003. Training Sanitary Vehicles -SPANISH	Minimum training standards for the sanitary professionals and drivers for sanitary vehicles	12/11/2003	Community of Madrid	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	(Madrid) Order 22.2014_Sanitary professional qualification - SPANISH	Professional qualification for sanitary professional and drivers for sanitary vehicles	13/03/2014	Community of Madrid	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	RD.22.14. Sanitary equipment for sanitary vehicles - SPANISH	Sanitary vehicles Professional staffing (Minimum) on vehicles	25/01/2014	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	RD. 836.2012. technical equipment for sanitary vehicles - SPANISH	Technical characteristics for sanitary vehicles description of professional staffing on vehicles	25/05/2012	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	Order PCI.488.2019_Civil protection. National strategy (Spain-Portugal) - SPANISH	Holistic approach for emergencies and civil protection	30/04/2019	Spain	LINK
SERMAS (Leader)	NAVID BEHZADI	Protocol The Kingdom of Spain and Republic or Portugal on cooperation in emergency situations - SPANISH	It establishes a mutual collaboration between the kingdom of Spain and the republic of Portugal	10/09/2019	Spain/ Portugal	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	Law 2.1985, civil protection	General low about civil protection	21/01/1985	Spain	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	Royal Decree 513/2017, approves the Regulation of fire protection installations.	Fire protection installations. Just in case that some infrastructure are involved in the Use Case	12/07/2017	Spain	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	BASIC HANDBOOK OF THE FOREST FIREFIGHTER (EXTREMADURA)	BASIC HANDBOOK OF THE FOREST FIREFIGHTER. SPAIN'S SIDE OF UC1. Operational protocol.		Spain/ Extremadura	LINK
AREU	Andrea Comelli Monica Ghinaglia	DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 2 gennaio 2018, n. 224 - Codice della protezione civile. (18G00011) –(GU n.17 del 22-1-2018)	Referring to the emergency plan for hydrogeological events, including forest fires, AREU cooperates, not only for the drafting of the plan, but also sending the most appropriate resources (human and technical) in case of medical aid is needed.		Italy	LINK
AREU	Andrea Comelli Monica Ghinaglia	Aggiornamento della direttiva regionale per la gestione organizzativa e funzionale del sistema di allertamento per i rischi naturali ai fini di protezione civile (d.p.c.m. 27/02/2004)	Referring to the emergency plan for hydrogeological events, including forest fires, AREU cooperates, not only for the drafting of the plan, but also sending the most appropriate resources (human and technical) in case of medical aid is needed.		Italy	LINK
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Law 10/2019, of April 11, on Civil Protection and Emergency Management of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura	Order actions in emergencies and regulate, within the framework of state and European legislation, the powers of the autonomous community in matters of civil protection	In force 17/20/2019, published DOE 17/04/2019	Spain/ Extremadura	-

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Territorial Plan of Civil Protection of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (PLATERCAEX)	The purpose of the plan is to prevent the loss of human life and property in different emergency situations. It contains the basic concepts to develop the operational structure of civil protection. Its scope is the territory of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura in terms of geographical scope and the general risks that may affect the autonomous community except for special risks that have their own planning.	DECREE 187/2019, of October 15. published in DOE No. 247 of December 26, 2019.	Spain/ Extremadura	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Forest fire fighting plan of the autonomous community of Extremadura (INFOEX)	It establishes the measures for the detection and extinction of forest fires and the resolution of the situations that arise from them. Its scope is all the mountains, understanding as such the lands defined in article 5 of the mountain law 10/2006.	Decree 52/2010, of March 5	Spain/Extremadura	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Law 17/2015, of July 9, on the National Civil Protection System	Establish the national civil protection system as an essential instrument to ensure the coordination, cohesion and effectiveness of public civil protection policies, and regulate the powers of the general administration of the state in the matter	In force on 10 January, 2016, published in BOE No. 164 of July 10, 2015	Spain	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	State Plan of Civil Protection for Emergencies due to forest fires	The objective of the state plan is to establish the organization and action procedures to ensure an effective response by all public administrations in emergency cases due to forest fires in which the national interest is present, as well as, in other cases, to provide the necessary support to the plans of the autonomous communities when they require it. The scope of action covers the entire national territory.	November 8, BOE November 7	Spain	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Protocol between the Kingdom of Spain and the Republic of Portugal on Technical Cooperation and Mutual Assistance in Civil Protection matters	The protocol covers scientific and technical cooperation between the two countries that, on a reciprocal basis, may request help from the other party in cases of emergency or catastrophe or in anticipation of these. The executing services will be the National Civil Protection Service of Portugal and the General Directorate of Civil Protection and Emergency of Spain.	In force on July 2, 1993, published in BOE No. 175 of July 23, 1993	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Treaty between the Kingdom of Spain and the Portuguese Republic on cross-border cooperation	Its purpose is to promote and legally regulate cross-border cooperation between Portuguese authorities and Spanish territorial entities within the scope of their respective competences. The treaty specifies the regions and municipalities of application.	In force on January 30, 2004, BOE 219 of September 12, 2003	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
TASSICA	Carmen Martín Curto	Additional protocol on mutual aid in case of forest fires	Its purpose is to establish the conditions and procedures for the provision of assistance or relief and the requirements for the provision of resources in the event of an emergency due to forest fires in border areas between Spain and Portugal. Applicable to border areas that, both of the Portuguese and Spanish side, they are made up of the bordering municipalities	BOE 34/02/7, 2018	Kingdom of Spain and de Republic of Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar	National Forest Fire Defense Plan (PNDFCI)	Increasing the territory's resilience to forest fires; Reducing the incidence of wildfires; Improving the effectiveness of attack and management of wildfires; Recovering and rehabilitating ecosystems; Adaptation of a functional and efficient organic structure	April 2006	Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar	Civil Protection National Plan of Emergency	National plan that seeks to set the guidelines of responses in case of natural disasters such as forest fires, earthquakes, flooding, rupture of dams, heatwaves, etc.	July 18 2008	Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar	Évora Municipal Emergency Plan	Establishing criteria and technical standards for the preparation and operationalization of civil protection emergency plans	July 2012	Évora, Portugal	
HESE	Miguel Gaspar	National Strategy of Adaptation to Climate Change	Aims to improve the level of knowledge on climate change and promote the integration of adaptation to climate change in sectoral policies and territorial planning instruments. The ENAAC also aims to help central, regional and local administration and policy makers to find the means and tools to implement	April 2010	Portugal	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
			adaptation solutions based on scientific and technical knowledge and best practices.			
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Spain	LINK

Table 35 – Legal Standard Identification for UC1 Spain – Portugal

7.2. UC2 – Slovakia - Italy

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
I SEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	Civil Protection Act	The purpose of this Act is to regulate the conditions for effective protection of life, health and property from the consequences of emergencies, as well as to establish the roles and responsibilities of state administration bodies, self-governing regions, municipalities and rights and obligations of natural persons and legal entities in ensuring civil protection.	05/2021	Slovakia	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	Danube River Protection Convention (DRPC)	DRPC - main objective is to ensure that surface waters and groundwater within the Danube River Basin are managed and used sustainably and equitably. This involves: (a) the conservation, improvement and rational use of surface water and groundwater, (b) preventive measures to control hazards originating from accidents involving floods, ice or hazardous substances, (c) measures to reduce the pollution loads entering the Black Sea from sources in the Danube River Basin.	10/1998	14 Danube countries	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	DANUBE DECLARATION	The declaration addresses the border-crossing problems along the Danube corridor, regarding environmental protection and the risk of floods, and is also in line with the EU Water Framework Directive.	9.2.2016	14 Danube countries	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	EU Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC	The Water Framework Directive stipulates that groundwater must achieve good quantitative status and good chemical status. Chemical quality refers to environmental quality standards for river basin specific pollutants. These standards specify maximum concentrations for specific water pollutants.	22.12.2000	Member States	LINK
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	DIRECTIVE 2004/35/CE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL	The purpose of this Directive is to establish a framework of environmental liability to prevent and remedy environmental damage.	21.4.2004	Member States	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
ISEMI (Leader)	Beata Korpesio	COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 1999/31/EC	The aim of this Directive is, by way of stringent operational and technical requirements on the waste and landfills, to provide for measures, procedures and guidance to prevent or reduce as far as possible negative effects on the environment, in particular the pollution of surface water, groundwater, soil and air, and on the global environment, including the greenhouse effect, as well as any resulting risk to human health, from landfilling of waste, during the whole life-cycle of the landfill.	26.4.1999	Member States	LINK
AREU	Andrea Comelli Monica Ghinaglia	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• DD.MM 25/2/86 e 21/3/86 per la codifica delle materie pericolose• Procedura attivazione della Scorta Nazionale Antidoti (SNA) Marzo 2015• D.Lgs. n. 334 del 17 agosto 1999 - Attuazione della direttiva 96/82/CE relativa al controllo dei pericoli di incidenti rilevanti connessi con determinate sostanze pericolose (Testo coordinato ad aggiornato al D.Lgs. 21 Settembre 2005 n. 238 di attuazione della direttiva 2003/105/CE che modifica la direttiva 96/82/CE sul controllo dei pericoli di incidenti rilevanti connessi con determinate sostanze pericolose) D.G.R. n. 15496 del 5 dicembre 2003• Direttiva Regionale Grandi Rischi: linee guida per la gestione delle emergenze chimico industriali (ai sensi della L.R. n. 1/2000, art. 3, comma 131)	Based on the documents listed above, AREU has implemented procedures and operating indications in order to manage an event with high risk of chemical or bacteriological contamination considering the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Precautions to be taken. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cooperation with the subjects assigned to the rescue phase.• Procedures to be adopted for an intervention that adequately protects the health personnel.• Identification of other priorities to be adopted for an accomplished and correct intervention to protect the intoxicated / contaminated.		Italy	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D.d.g n. 10872 Nov. 2014 Protocollo operativo in materia di Bioterrorismo • Presidenza Consiglio dei Ministri 2004 Piano Sanitario di Emergenza in caso di attacco terroristico con aggressivi chimici <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreto Ministero dell'Interno 13 Febbraio 2001 "Adozione dei criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi • Decreto del 13 Febbraio 2001 Criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri del 28 Giugno 2011 • Indirizzi operativi per l'attivazione e la gestione dei moduli sanitari in caso di catastrofe - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri - Repertorio 1993 del 24 Giugno 2016 				
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Slovakia	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Austria	LINK

Table 36 – Legal Standard Identification for UC2 Slovakia – Italy

7.3. UC3 – Bulgaria – Greece

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev	DISASTER PROTECTION ACT of the Republic of Bulgaria	<p>This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters. Art. 4. The main principles of disaster protection shall be:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. right of protection for every person;2. privilege of the rescue of the human life before the rest activities upon the protection;3. publicity of the information for the risks of disasters and for the activities of the bodies of the executive power upon the protection in case of disasters;4. privilege of the preventive measures when ensuring the protection;5. responsibility for the implementation of the measures of protection;6. submission of forces and resources for protection stage by stage. <p>Art. 5. (amend. – SG 80/11, in force from 14.10.2011) Disaster protection shall be provided on a national, district and municipal level and carried out through:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. performing preventive activity;2. performing protection activities in the event of disaster upon occurrence thereof;3. relief and recovery;	Prom. SG. 102/19 Dec 2006, last amend. SG. 80/14 Oct 2011	Republic of Bulgaria	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
			4. resource insurance; 5. provision and acceptance of relief funds.			
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev	MINISTRY OF THE INTERIOR ACT Prom. SG. 53/27 Jun 2014	Section V. Provision of Fire Safety and Protection in Fires, Disasters and Emergencies Section V "a". Art. 17. (1) The activities of providing fire safety and protection in fires, disasters and emergencies shall be carried out by the authorities of fire safety and protection of the population under the conditions and procedure of this act Section VI. Enabling access of citizens to the emergency services through the National Emergency Calls System with SEN 112 (new - SG 14/15)	41796	Republic of Bulgaria	
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev	ACT ON THE NATIONAL EMERGENCY SYSTEM WITH A SINGLE EUROPEAN CALL NUMBER 112, Prom. SG. 102/28 Nov 2008	This Act shall regulate the structure and functions of the National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112 The National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112, the responsibilities for its setting up, maintenance and development, as well as the rights and the obligations of the citizens using the single European emergency call number 112. The receiving centers of emergency calls to the SEN 112, herein after referred to as Centres "112" are territorial units of Directorate "National System 112" of the Ministry of Interior (MI). The	39780	Republic of Bulgaria	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
			National Emergency Centers are: the National Medical Coordination Centre, the Emergency Medical Assistance Centers, the chief and regional directorates of the Ministry of Interior, Executive Agency Maritime Administration and the Mountain Rescue Service at the Bulgarian Red Cross.			
BDI (Leader)	Yantsislav Yanakiev	Act on the Management and Functioning of the System of National Security Protection	This act defines the national security protection system, the tasks and responsibilities of the institutions and services included in this system, the coordination between them, and the control over their operation	Promulgated , SG No. 61/11.08.2015, effective 1.11.2015	Republic of Bulgaria	

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
AREU	Andrea Comelli Monica Ghinaglia	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Decreto del 13 Febbraio 2001 Criteri di massima per l'organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri del 28 Giugno 2011Indirizzi operativi per l'attivazione e la gestione dei moduli sanitari in caso di catastrofe - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri - Repertorio 1993 del 24 Giugno 2016Individuazione della Centrale Remota Operazioni Soccorso Sanitario per il coordinamento dei soccorsi sanitari urgenti nonché dei Referenti Sanitari Regionali in caso di emergenza NazionaleProgramma Nazionale di Soccorso per il Rischio Sismico (DPCM 14 gennaio 2014)Linee guida INSARAG 2015 (International Search and Rescue Advisory Group)	The documents mentioned, define the response methods of receivers, of human resources, logistical and structural resources and special teams in case of regional, extra-regional, national accident of the "seismic event" type. The "USAR" (urban search and rescue) teams work in cooperation with the National Fire Brigade, according to organizational, managerial and operational standards aimed to encouraging the development of operational units for the search and rescue of those missing under rubble, constituted by personnel in possession of high qualifications, in line with the "good practices" defined in the international field by the guidelines of the International Search And Rescue Advisory Group (INSAGAR, latest update in 2020). Urban search and rescue is a type of technical rescue operation that involves the location, extrication, and initial medical stabilization of victims trapped in an urban area, namely structural collapse due to natural disasters, war, terrorism or accidents, mines and collapsed trenches.		Italy	
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Xenokratis (Ministerial Decision 1299/2003–Government Gazette 423 B/10-04-2003)	National General Plan for Civil Protection, aiming at effective response to catastrophic phenomena for the protection of life, health and property of citizens, as well as the protection of the natural environment	10.04.2003	Greece	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	National Law 4662/20 (OGG27 A 4662/07.02.2020)	National Crisis Management and Risk Management Mechanism, Restructuring of the National Secretariat for Civil Protection, upgrading a system of voluntary policy protection, reorganization of the Fire and other provisions.	07.02.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	National Special Human Loss Management Plan	This plan defines a system for the proper organization and coordination of stakeholders and services, to effectively manage incidents with numerous deaths as a result of physical, technological (including biological, chemical, radiological and nuclear events) and other disasters as well as criminal and terrorist acts.	18.12.2019	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Action Plan Egkelados	General Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes	30.01.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Template Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes for the municipalities of the Hellenic territory	A template for the setting up of emergency response plan for Municipalities of the Hellenic Territory	19.06.2020	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Action Plan "Dardanos"	General Action Plan for emergency response and short-term management of floods impacts	6.12.2019	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Joint Ministerial Decision 31822/1542/E103 (OGG B 1108/21.07.2010)	Incorporation of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC in the Greek National Law	21.07.2010	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Flood Risk Management Plan for the Water District of Central Macedonia	Implementation of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC in the Water District close to the area of interest of Demonstrator #3	05.07.2018	Greece	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction / Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	PD128 (OGG9717 A 228/07.12.2016	Incorporation of the ATEX 214 “equipment” Directive 2014/34/EU–Equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres in the Greek National Law	07.12.2016	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	PD42 (OGG493 A 44/21.02.2003)	Incorporation of ATEX 137 “workplace” Directive 1999/92/EC– Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers potentially at risk from explosive atmospheres in the Greek National Law	21.02.2003	Greece	LINK
KEMEA	John Tsaloukidis	Action Plan Herakleitos	General Action Plan for emergency response due to large scale technological accidents (General SATAME)	06.02.2020	Greece	LINK
HRT	Iosif Vourvachis Dimitris Iliadis	INSARAG GUIDELINES 2020	he INSARAG Guidelines provides a methodology to guide countries affected by a sudden-onset disaster causing large-scale structural collapse, as well as international USAR Teams responding in the affected country	2020	UN	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Bulgaria	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Greece	LINK

Table 37 – Legal Standard Identification for UC3 Bulgaria – Greece

7.4. UC4 – Norway – Netherlands – Denmark

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction/Scope	Publication date / In force	Country / Region	Link
AREU	Andrea Comelli Monica Ghinaglia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreto Ministero dell’Interno 13 Febbraio 2001 “Adozione dei criteri di massima per l’organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi Decreto del 13 Febbraio 2001 Criteri di massima per l’organizzazione dei soccorsi sanitari nelle catastrofi - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri del 28 Giugno 2011 Indirizzi operativi per l’attivazione e la gestione dei moduli sanitari in caso di catastrofe - Direttiva della Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri - Repertorio 1993 del 24 Giugno 2016 	<p>Actually, a maritime disaster scenario is unlikely in Lombardy, but it is conceivable in contests as lakes, rivers or streams.</p> <p>We do not have specific reference documentation but we are investigating the issue with our colleagues of Emergency call dispatch points in charge of Lakes Area.</p>		Italy	
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) - Adoption: 1973 (Convention), 1978 (1978 Protocol), 1997 (Protocol - Annex VI); Entry into force: 2 October 1983 (Annexes I and II).	The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) is the main international convention covering prevention of pollution of the marine environment by ships from operational or accidental causes.	Adoption: 1973 (Convention), 1978 (1978 Protocol)	International	
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Denmark	LINK

Table 38 – Legal Standard Identification for UC3 Norway – Netherlands - Denmark

7.5. Common to all use cases

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction/Scope	Publication date/In force	Country/Region	Link
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	M/487 EN. PROGRAMMING MANDATE ADDRESSED TO CEN, CENELEC AND ETSI TO ESTABLISH SECURITY STANDARDS	This Mandate concerns the development of a work program for the definition of European Standards and other standardization deliverables in the area of SECURITY. The program will take note of all aspects linked to the different specific products, systems, procedures and protocols that should be covered by standards to assist the EU to ensure that security is better and consistently addressed in different security landscapes. This Mandate has an exclusively civil application focus.	17/02/2011	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	DECISION No 1313/2013/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL	1. This Decision shall apply to cooperation in the field of civil protection (a) prevention and preparedness actions inside the Union. (b) actions to assist with the response to immediate adverse consequences of a disaster inside or outside the Union. 2. Shall take into account the special needs (e.g. isolated, islands, overseas countries) in terms of prevention of.	13/12/2013	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	COUNCIL DECISION of 23 October 2001 establishing a Community mechanism to facilitate reinforced cooperation in civil protection assistance interventions	In the event of a major emergency within the Community, or imminent threat thereof, which causes, or is capable of causing, transboundary effects or which may result in a call for assistance from one or more Member States, there is a need for relevant notification to be made as appropriate through an established	15/11/2001	Member States	LINK

Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction/Scope	Publication date/In force	Country/Region	Link
			reliable common emergency communication and information system.			
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	COUNCIL DECISION of 8 November 2007 establishing a Community Civil Protection Mechanism (recast) (Text with EEA relevance) (2007/779/EC, Euratom)	The Mechanism should facilitate the civil protection response to all types of major emergencies occurring inside or outside the Community, including natural and man-made disasters, acts of terrorism and technological, radiological and environmental accidents, including accidental marine pollution. Civil protection assistance may be required in all of these emergencies to complement the response capabilities of the affected country.	11/12/2007	Member States	LINK
NOVOTEC	Ignacio Hernandez	The national disaster management system	The EU document shows who is the National Disaster Management System of the countries. Exceled overview could be a source of more information.	2021	Member States	LINK

Table 39 – Legal Standard Identification common for all use cases

8. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
UC	Use Case
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
C&C	Command and Control
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
GA	Grant Agreement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GIS	Geographic Information System
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage

Table 40 - Glossary